

ANNEXES

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Note:

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Annex 1: Table summarizing WP4 cases presented in annex 2

Case number	Cases brief description	Case number	Cases brief description
1	Local Bakery , research project, France	27	PTV , Wine Technology Platform –Living Lab, Spain
2	ETP Food for Life , Europe	28	GO VITINNAT , Living Lab, Spain
3	Echt Schwarzwald , regional branding, Germany	29	SRIP HRANA , Research and innovation partnership for sustainable food systems, Slovenia
4	Flexiprocess , a sustainable (agroecological) field to fork concept for cereals, research project, France	30	NORWEGIAN PARTNERSHIP FOR A HEALTHIER DIET , population nutrition partnership, Norway
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6	Sud de France , regional branding, France	32	FOOD FOR LIFE FRANCE , technological platform for food innovation, France
7	ALIBETOPIAS , Living Lab & networking event, Spain	33	RESEARCH ASSOCIATION OF THE GERMAN FOOD INDUSTRY , research support association, Germany
8	CLUSAGA - Galician Food cluster , Spain	34	Portugal FOODS , innovation platform (cluster), Portugal
9	FOOD + i , regional cluster from the Ebro valley – living lab, Spain	35	VALORIAL , innovation cluster, France
10	GESVINA , a supra-autonomous operating group for sustainable viticulture, Spain	36	MILAN PACT AWARDS (MPA) , collaboration toward sustainable food systems, International
11	Italy - Israel , international scientific partnership on hydroponics cultivation, Italy	37	SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE (SAGRI) , Erasmus +, Italy/Athens
12	OSAF , Observatory on Smart Agri-food, Italy	38	CULTURAL CHANGE 4 INCLUSION , civil society initiative for social inclusion, Italy
13	HUBFARM , digitalisation platform, Italy	39	RADIX , civil society initiative sustainable alternatives to undeclared work, Italy
14	ACTIA , Association de coordination technique pour l'industrie agro-alimentaire, France	40	FOOD FOR LIFE SPAIN , technological platform, Spain
15	TKI, TOP SECTOR AGRIFOOD , innovation platform (cluster), the Netherlands	41	VITARTIS , regional cluster, Spain
16	Pôle Vitagloria , competition pole, France	42	CEET , agro-logistics, R&I project, Netherlands
17	Milan Food Policy , food policy, Italy	43	Greek National Technology platform , Greece
18	Milan Food Waste Hubs , food policy project, Italy	44	Cluster Agrifood Nazionale C.L.A.N / Italy
19	MiRi , food policy project, Italy	45	WAGRALIM , cluster, Belgium
20	Planet project , Erasmus +, Italy, Austria, France and the Netherlands	46	BIM FISHERY IMPROVEMENT PROJECTS , Multi-stakeholders; innovation platform, Ireland
21	REINWASTE , Zero inorganic waste research project, Emilia-Romagna, Andalusia, PACA	47	INNOVATION MARKETING PROGRAM , enhancing sustainable fishery products, Finland
22	Mountain and Rural Areas Protocol , policy project, Italy	48	NATURSKANSOM , collective national brand, Denmark

23	AGRICOLTURA 100 , survey and annual report on the contribution of agriculture to sustainability, Italy	49	POLE MER MEDITERRANEE , competitive cluster, France
24	ECOTROPHILIA , The student awards of food innovation, Europe	50	NCE SEAFOOD INNOVATION , seafood cluster, Norway
25	FOOD SCIENCE FESTIVAL , Italy	51	Sustainable Food Procurement , Copenhagen, Denmark
26	PTEPA , Spanish Technological Platform of Fishing and Aquaculture -Living lab, Spain	52	Sustainable Procurement of "early vegetables" , municipality policy project, Vienna, Austria

Annex 2: WP4 case studies

Case 1: Local Bakery, France

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country "Wheat/Human/Sourdough" agro-food ecosystem, France

One or two key features: Biological and socio-cultural diversity and low-input

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): ANR Project 2014 - 2018

DESCRIPTION

Photo banner (France)

An illustration ©INRAE

History of co-creation between actors: In 2014, the ANR project was set up with 8 partners from research, 2 farmer's associations and over 30 bakers and farmers

Which ambitions and objectives: whether and how the diversity of human artisanal practices contribute to the sustainability of the bread making food chain.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: from individual research approaches

towards collective hands-on actions in bakeries and agro-ecological production fields.

What external input and output: state subvention via the national research funds and time and resources investments of partners.

Summary: As a whole, this project shows that the whole food chain must be studied to establish what are the levers to improve the quality and sustainability of food. It shows the interest of participatory research projects including scientists, professionals and citizens to address questions and obtain relevant results on food systems.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
(Artisanal) Bakery	Bakers	Wheat flour, water, sourdough	Baking	Safety	Specificities of Bakery environment provide unique qualities	4 year project duration reveals evidenced options
Agro-ecological production field	Farmers, agronomists	Ancient & modern wheat landraces & varieties	Agro-ecological production	Agroecological law	New opportunities for wheat landraces and sourdoughs bread	Product innovation in 4 yrs feasible
	Microbiologists	Yeast, lactic acid bacteria	Fermentation	Safety healthiness	Microbiome research provides opportunities	
	Psychosociologists	Bread-making practices, citizen representation	Interviews with bakers and citizen	Consumer social links appreciation	More locally diverse bakery products	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Bakery experiences	Belief in artisanal production, sharing on bread-making practices	Interactions between farmer- bakery and bakeries, between rural and urban bakeries	Promoting sourdough bread diversity and quality	Local clusters included citizens
Profound knowledge of agro-ecological production	Capacity to include landraces and mixed crops	Scientists, farmers, bakers and citizens working hand-in-hand	Favouring local products adapted to diverse environments	Not yet elaborated with other players in the market
Expertise in microbial ecology	Ability to exchange knowledge on fermentation and microbial diversity		Promoting microbial diversity in food chain	Built a strong network of bakers, farmer-bakers and microbiologists who act together to promote local value chain development

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

As a whole, this project shows that the whole food chain must be studied to establish what are the levers to improve the quality and sustainability of food. It shows the interest of participatory research projects including scientists, professionals and citizens to address questions and obtain relevant results on food systems

Case 2: European Platform Food for Life, Europe

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: ETP FOOD FOR LIFE / European Platform

One or two key features: Innovation platform at EU level for the Food Industry

Source: <https://etp.fooddrinkurope.eu/>

Status: Running initiative (2005-Present)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The ETP 'Food for Life' Vision for 2020 and beyond, launched in Brussels in July 2005, identified the need for an effective integration of strategically-focused, trans-national, concerted research in the nutritional, food and consumer sciences and food chain management. In 2005, the ETP 'Food for Life' became fully operational after the establishment of the Board, Operational Committee and 7 Working Groups with representation of all stakeholders across Europe. The first Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) was published in September 2007 after extensive consultations with all relevant stakeholders through face-to-face meetings across Europe and via web-based activities.

Which ambitions and objectives: ETPs develop research and innovation agendas and roadmaps for action at EU and national level to be supported by both private and public funding. They mobilise stakeholders to deliver on agreed priorities, share information across the EU and help deliver solutions to major challenges of key concern to citizens.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The secretariat is maintained by FoodDrinkEurope. Decisions are taken by the ETP Leadership team, composed by 15 members of academia and industry. There are 6 additional working groups: Nutrition and health, Consumers, Food safety, Food production, Food processing, Packaging. There are no funding activities or membership fees.

What external input and output: A platform for quicker and more effective, consumer-oriented food innovation, by enabling the appropriate environment for pre-competitive research and competitive consortium establishment; A forum for ensuring an effective multidisciplinary/integrating approach and exchange of best practices; An effective means of generating and leveraging funding; Better education and training of persons in various disciplines; Durable career opportunities within the European food and drink sector.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
European Platform	Food industry	Strategic Research and Innovation agenda	Network	EU action	Food Systems Approach	2005-Present
Innovation	Universities and RTOs at EU level	Network, Events, Workshops	Collaboration with other ETPs	No funding offered or received	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda	2016-Present: Renewal of governance
Food Industry	Link to EU Food industry federation	Position papers	Think tank approach	Sustained by FoodDrinkEurope	Innovation Action Plan	
	Link to EU platforms	Interaction with the EC DG RTD			Workshops with relevant stakeholders at EU level	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network	Joint industry – academic collaboration	EU network of companies, universities and RTOs	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and Action Plan	NFTPs platform, FoodDrinkEurope EIT-Food, ETPs network, EU platforms
Innovation				
Strategic vision in EU				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Main sources: ETP Food for Life (FoodDrinkEurope secretariat)

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Case 3: Echt Schwarzwald, Germany

Name of the food systems co-creation case: Echt Schwarzwald brand

One or two key features: collective place brand, local strategy

Status : running since 2008

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: To countervail the decrease of the use of agricultural grazing areas and to protect the traditional natural landscape of the Black Forest, the brand Echt Schwarzwald was launched in 2008. The main objective of the brand was to create added value (via price premium for specialty products) for local farmers to keep grassland farming attractive and profitable

Which ambitions and objectives: preserve the traditional natural landscape, offer price premium for typical local quality (mainly beef) products, animal welfare

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: first, the natural park members and the Ortenau community worked together on the idea with a consulting firm, then the governance was given to the public-private association Echt Schwarzwald e.V.

What external input and output: in the beginning, public support; estimation of 10-12% price premium increasing farmers' incomes

Photo banner (including country)

An illustration

Joint marketing for quality local products from the Black Forest, Germany

Spezialitäten aus den Naturparken des Schwarzwaldes

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)	
local scale; natural park Schwarzwald Mitte/Nord, in the South-West of Germany	local communities, two natural parks, the association with ca. 100 members	regional identity and natural-cultural heritage	labelling of products after quality check	high quality requirements for products, audits	public support for brand development in the first 4 years	contribution of the brand initiative to the preservation of the natural landscape	in the first 4 years, public support
local production, processing, sales	local farmers, butchers, restaurants	local quality food products, mainly beef, pork, liquor, honey, milk	production, processing, distribution	fulfilment of origin and quality requirements	After 4 years, brand management taken over by private actors	valorization and added-value for local quality healthy products, increasing farmers' incomes	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
public-private partnership; complementary knowledge from two natural parks, several communities, consulting firm	communication between different partners rather difficult, different ways of thinking	local public-private partnership with joint promotional activities	preserve the traditional landscape, by developing a marketing concept for high quality products	
farmers, butchers, restaurants providing high quality food products			the ecological and animal welfare dimension could be enforced	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The focus of the marketing strategy is on the economic (price premium for farmers) and environmental (protection of the typical natural-cultural landscape) dimension. According to a brand member, the ecological and animal welfare dimension should be enforced.

Main sources: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41254-016-0049-z>

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Case 4: Flexiprocess, France

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Flexiprocess, a sustainable field to fork concept for cereals

One or two key features: coupling of agroecology and bioeconomy

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Started in 2015, ongoing

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: In 2015, a typical agroecological production field for cereals and legumes has been coupled to manufacturing and consumption practices.

Which ambitions and objectives: the objective has been to reduce fertilizer usage via a systemic change including all actors in the chain.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: It is a R&D-driven initiative that gradually included all actors, even health professionals, in the cereal and legume chain.

What external input and output: The French law on agroecology and the French national strategy for healthy and sustainable nutrition have been guiding the process.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Agro-ecological production fields	Farmers (wheat and legumes),	Cereals and legumes	Novel rotation schemes	Law on agroecology R&D support	Reduction of fertilizers, healthy soils, biodiversity	> 10 years
manufacturing & consumption sites	technology suppliers		Novel fractionation and separation techn			5 – 10 years
	pasta makers, bakers	Pasta, pizza, bread, pastry	Flexible food manufacturing tools	Safety in processing	New healthy and sustainable products	< 10 years
	consumers, health experts		Decision support tools for consumption, health	Healthy & sustainable diet strategy	Nutrition guidelines and high level of appreciation	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Knowledge about each unit operation	Changing production methods	Rotation schemes developed by cereal and legume farmers	Zero pesticides	Contributing to the national agro-ecology law
Knowledge about each resource and product	Changing recipes	New cooperation between food manufacturers and technology suppliers	Innovative ecotechnologies in milling	Reinforcing the national food strategy
Excellent service provision	Willingness to test new products	Cooperation across the chain between diverse actors	New healthy & sustainable diets	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

This has been a commonly designed project and executed by a consortium that had a common focus on agroecology, value chains, nutrition and health as well as the wider bioeconomy. It became a public-private cooperation trajectory for years, where each actors brought in its strength and willingness to adapt their activities based on input from others. The innovative character was shared by all.

Main sources: DOI: 10.1016/j.tifs.2019.02.027

DOI: 10.1007/s10806-021-09850-7

<https://www.strategie.gouv.fr/publications/une-alimentation-saine-durable-rapport-lassemblee-nationale>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP4

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Case 5: Agro Energy Hohenhohe, Germany

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country **AgroEnergie Hohenlohe One or two**

key features: Eco-village, zero loss

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running since 2001

Photo banner (including country)

An illustration
From Biogas production
to an eco village

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: AgroEnergie Hohenlohe GmbH was funded as private commercial company. Originally the main goal of the company was to convert pig slurry from his animal husbandry into money via anaerobic digestion. Then, it was extended to marketable digestate, heat and energy delivery to the village with new village initiatives

Which ambitions and objectives: valorizing co-products and creating an eco-village. **Evolution of their governance model and organisation:** from individual farmer to joint venture with other companies, to a community initiative, led by the mayor and involved of citizens.

What external input and output: state subvention for biogas production was the trigger; then new market opportunities and green vision of the nearby village.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
territorial scale,	local farmers, own logistics	Biogas,	Recycling	National legislation Subventions	technological, business & social innovations	Since 2001, stepwise extension
Village-rural interface	eco-villagers (heat) & Town Hall,	dried fertilizer for targeted applications	bioenergy conversion and delivery	limitation for feed-in tariffs	valorization of organic waste, new products & markets for local producers	2004 extension for biogas
	e-car company	'manure', co-products fruit & vegetables	bio-fertilizer processing		odors, jobs created.	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Entrepreneurship	Adapting to resource availability	Joint eco-village building	Green environment	Network of energy villages: green focus
Knowledge of renewable resources (co-products)	new market opportunities for bio-fertilizers	Utilizing complementary competences	Autonomous	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The initiator had a future vision: Starting from biogas production, continuing to close nutrient cycles / loops, having 100% residues as input, producing nutrient salts and ability to produce specific fertilisers fit for exporting nutrients in other regions or sectors. His focus is on optimal nutrient management and plant (crop) production, become fully independent from available land for spreading nutrients (both on the input and the output side), thanks to a new pilot plant for nutrient recovery at full scale. Further elaborating with the village the concept of an energy – eco – village.

Main sources: NoAW project; ref. hal-02624927

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS, WP4

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Case 6: Sud de France, France

Name of the food systems co-creation case: Sud de France brand

One or two key features: Collective place brand, regional development strategy

Status : Running since 2006

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The former president of the region Languedoc- Roussillon, Georges Frêche, launched the collective Sud de France brand in 2006, as he wished to create a common regional identity, to bring the region out of its seclusion, to activate local resources for internationalization, and to support small agrifood actors. In 2015, the brand was extended to the new region Occitanie.

Which ambitions and objectives: local consumption, support of small agrifood actors, quality healthy products, heritage and local know-how, regional economic development **Evolution of their governance model and organisation:** from a top-down public to a collective approach including regional stakeholders (agrifood companies, consumers, . . .). **What external input and output:** public subvention for promotional activities (communication, distribution support); new market opportunities for small agrifood actors and valorisation quality territorial products.

An illustration
Joint marketing for typical
local products from the
Occitanie region, France

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
regional scale	public regional actors (regional government, chamber of agriculture etc.)	regional identity and heritage	labelling of products after quality check	quality requirements per product chain	public support for marketing (communication and distribution)	positive outcomes for the region (awareness, conservation of local heritage, economic development)	since 2006, 2015 extension from Languedoc-Roussillon to the Occitanie region
local production and processing, sales at local and international level	1700 farmers, food SMEs, distributors, consumers (local and international)	13000 different food products labelled, mainly wine, fruit and vegetables, fish	production, processing, distribution, consumption	fulfilment of origin and quality requirements	appreciation by local producers and consumers	valorization and added-value for local quality healthy products, inclusion of small players	Stepwise inclusion of more actors

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
former president of the region acting as institutional entrepreneur, clear vision	new regional government adopting an already established brand	regional public-private cluster with joint promotional activities	common regional brand identity	
knowledge of local quality food production, willingness-to-pay of consumers	marketing and distribution opportunities for newly entering brand members	'brand family'	joint development of quality standards per chain	joint vision between different beverage and food chain clusters

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), . . .)

The initiator of the brand had a clear future vision: economic development of the region, inclusion of small economic actors, protection of local heritage and know-how. These sustainability values are inherent to the brand and shared by its adherents and the consumers of the Sud de France food products.

Main sources: <https://sud-de-france.com/>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP4

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Case 7: Alibetopias, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: ALIBETOPIAS – Living Lab / Spain

One or two key features: Networking event

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

ALIBETOPIAS

Nuevos territorios en Alimentación y Bebidas

Description

History of co-creation between actors: Since 2015 this event was organised with the aim of create a meeting point to explore new synergies and promote knowledge that helps companies in the sector to gain size and be more competitive in the international market. Research groups, technological centres, private companies and other members of the Food for Life-Spain Technological Platform, are in need of events that cultivate relationships between the different parts involved in the food industry on innovation matters. The event is also open to non-associated companies and individuals, which is a good opportunity to share points of view.

Which ambitions and objectives: Alibetopías is a meeting point to explore new synergies and promote knowledge that helps companies in the sector to grow and be more competitive in international markets. Alibetopías is the star day for innovation in the Spanish agri-food sector in which ideas are identified, projects are shown, results are shared in a participatory and collaborative environment in order to go further and be able to face a future full of challenges in which the innovation is key to success.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: The Spanish Federation of Food and Beverage Industries (FIAB) and the Food for Life Spain Technological Platform, with the support of the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) have elaborated a Strategic Framework for the Food and Drinks Industry whose main objective is contributing to the improvement of the Spanish economy.

What external input and output: This event is hold once a year, and every year features top-level speakers linked to the sector that share the latest trends in RDI projects. Commonly, it is structured in 3 main thematic blocks: Technological Startups, New Technologies and Business Experiences. Every single technology is assessed by the participants in order to carry out the different possibilities to develop innovative products and/or processes. In addition, the administration bodies that are also present in the event are involved in considering funding opportunities for those innovative projects.

ORGANISERS

SPONSORS

COLABORATORS

Figure. Current organisers, sponsors and other collaborations

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
New products	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products (sources, raw materials)	12-24 months
New processes and techniques	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products, Food technologies and processes	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (energy, waste treatments, packaging)	12-36 months
Better products	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Market	Competitors and prices	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	6-24 months
Better processes	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food technologies and processes	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Competitors and prices	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	6-24 months
Neetworking, Ideas sharing	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities, funding boards	Promotion projects, new contacts, B2B relationships	Projects (individual/consortia)	Market	Competitors, funding, ideas	More ambitious and consolidated projects	1-2 week

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + Corporations Products, processes	High flexibility Willingness to be applied to their products/processes	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that share the same interests
Research Centres/ Universities/ Startups Basic Research and first approach	Low flexibility They are based on scientific evidences and market behaviour	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They are more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes) goals, but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in.
Technological Centres/ Startups Applied research and try new tools	Medium flexibility Intermediate scale to test different technologies	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals but they depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the public (and even) private funding are well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, new created boundings will be well aligned with sustainability projects and trends.

Case 8: Clusaga, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: «Galician Food Cluster»/ Spain

One or two key features: Regional Cluster

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: The food sector is one of the strategic sectors in Galicia both due to its size and its economic and social importance. In this area, the Galician Food Cluster (Clusaga) operates in an organized structure of the Galician food sector, in a broad sense, integrating companies, as well as research and innovation entities and other organizations, in cooperation processes that allow obtaining benefits derived from the application of collaborative actions and projects and achieving a critical mass that allows strengthening the international competitiveness and visibility of the sector. Clusaga was founded in 2010.

Which ambitions and objectives: Four final objectives and a fifth instrument are defined for the promotion of the dynamics of cooperation, parallel to competition, between all the agents of the chain value.

- Incorporate the cluster companies into the innovation and digitization strategy.
- Strengthen the ability to adapt and position the cluster companies in the markets.
- Incorporate the companies of the cluster in the strategy of the circular economy and the bioeconomy to favor the transition towards a more sustainable sector.
- Promote the development of new processes and sustainable products and healthy, safe foods and encourage more responsible consumption.
- Consolidate the leadership of the cluster in the food sector.

Evolution of their governance model and organization:

The structure is based on five areas:

- Board of Directors: The direction and administration of the association will be exercised by the President, the Board of Directors and the General Assembly.
- UNITEC (association).
- Sustainability and Circular Economy Commission.
- Innovation and R&D Commission.
- Markets and Internationalization Commission.

What external input and output: Planning and support service for innovation projects for SMEs, with actions ranging from carrying out innovation and digitization diagnoses to adapted action plans.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Competitive intelligence tool	SMEs, corporations	Analysis of new products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	Competitive surveillance	12-36 months
Internationalization plans	SMEs, corporations	Strategic international marketing plan	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Competitors, prices	Increase their competitiveness in foreign markets	12-36 months
Circularize service	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products.	12-36 months
Implementation of innovation plans	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Diagnosis of innovation	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Action plan	Differentiate themselves from their competitors and gain an advantage	12-36 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ...?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + corporations. Products, processes, market	Low flexibility concrete plans, amortization of projects	They usually become partners in RD/sustainability projects	Business innovation allows companies to differentiate themselves from their competitors and gain an advantage	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/Universities/Associations Research and Dissemination	Medium flexibility They are based on scientific evidences, generation of technological knowledge	They usually become partners in RD/sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology and its dissemination	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Technological Centres Applied research	Medium flexibility Competitive improvement of companies and their contribution to the economic development of their environment	They usually become partners in RD/sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/tradeoffs),): Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the public (and even) private funding are well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, they will comply with the rules and goals even if they are not the partner that is developing a project or a task because the whole project is considered as a single result.

Case 9: Food +i, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: FOOD+i (Regional Cluster from the *Ebro Valley*) – Living Lab / Spain
One or two key features: Regional Cluster
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: FOOD+i is a private, non-profit entity, that brings together leading companies, institutions, technology and research centers from the Ebro Valley. Nowadays it counts with more than 100 partners.

Which ambitions and objectives: Their main objective is the competitive improvement of the companies and associates, by promoting living-labs, encounter spaces, activities and innovational projects. Its motto is "Seek new horizons for your company. EXPLORE, CONNECT, INNOVATE with food+i". In order to do that, they create an operational networking to dinamize the food industry sector, they seek for a business strengthening.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: FOOD+i is a private business organization that works for the region. They are formed by **Board of Directors** (president, vice president and vocals) and a **Food+i Team** (cluster manager, head of national projects, head of EU projects, financial manager, and other project managers).

What external input and output: The Ebro valley is currently the main Food Production HUB in Spain. 25% of companies conforme it with 36% of the entire turnover of the sector and 33% of the total number of jobs . It represents a leading space at European level that is willing to mark the present and future of the sector.

Pic 1. Current governance model and organization

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a *GAME*):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Digitalization	SMEs and Technological Centers	Competitive Intelligence	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	Viability study to create Competitive Intelligence	12-36 months
Innovation	Technological Centers and Research centers	More sustainability, innovative and efficiency technologies	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (Packaging, conservation,)	12-36 months
Posicioning/ Representation / Competitivity	Partners, Companies, Associations, Technological Platforms	Promotion activities, financing them	New business opportunities supporting the innovation advances	Private funding	Competitors and prices	New business opportunities	12 months - 3 years
Bioeconomy	Partners, Companies, Associations, Technological Platforms	Inversion attraction, support for start-ups, investors and spin-offs.	Creation of a platform as a connecting point for everyone	Private funding	Competitors and local regulations	More sustainable processes through circular economy	5 months aprox

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + Technological Centers Competitive intelligence models	Medium flexibility Stablish plans and project	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/ Technological Centers Basic Research and Innovation	Medium flexibility They are based on scientific evidences, they generate scientific knowledge	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to be more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes)	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Partners / Companies / Associations Apply research and find new business oportunities	Medium flexibility Competitive improvement of companies and their contribution to economic development	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They usually try to be focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals but they mostly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in. They search for new ideas in research centers

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the public (and even) private funding are well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, they will comply with the rules and goals even if they are not the partner that is developing a project or a task because the whole project is considered as a single result.

Case 10: Gesvina, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: GESVIÑA– Living Lab / Spain

One or two key features: Operational Group

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: The creation of supra-autonomous Operational Groups is one of the key tools in the execution of the National Rural Development Program 2014-2020 in terms of productive and sustainable agriculture to promote innovation in the agri-food and forestry sector. This is the grouping of agents with different profiles with common interests, such as farmers, ranchers, companies, research or training centers, who come together to implement innovative mechanisms or practices in order to provide a joint and multisectoral response to a problem or need.

Which ambitions and objectives: GESVIÑA is a supra-autonomous operating group whose objective is sustainable viticulture of the Atlantic vineyard by reducing phytosanitary products, training the sector in calibration of application equipment, and the use of plant covers to counteract erosion and improve biological activity and fertility, reducing or eliminating herbicides.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: The supraautonomous operating group encompasses the regions of Galicia, Asturias and the Basque Country. It is coordinated by the company Sociedad Arousana Wine Cooperative (Winery Paco&Lola) and the Instituto Food Quality Galician (INGACAL - EVEGA), NEIKER Basque Institute for Agricultural Research and Development SA, the Service Regional Research and Development Agri-food of the Principality of Asturias (SERIDA), the Quality Wine Association of Cangas (Cangas Denomination of Origin) and the Galician Business-University Foundation (FEUGA).

What external input and output: In the first phase of creation of the O.G GESVIÑA, coordination meetings were held between the interlocutors, as well as dissemination sessions and the search for new partners for the Group, contact was established with other G.O.s with a similar theme and the Project that will be presented in the second phase was drafted.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a *GAME*):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
New products	Universities, Research Centers	More sustainability, innovative and efficient products	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products and positive effects in health	12-36 months
New processes and techniques	Technological Centers and Research centers	More sustainability, innovative and efficient techniques	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (energy, waste treatments)	12-36 months
Representation/ Implementation of innovation plans	Partners, Companies, Federations, Associations	Promotion activities, financing, Interactive sessions know-how	Support of created projects	Private funding	Competitors and prices	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	12-18 months
Administration and regulation	Regulatory Council, Organisations, Federations, Administration	Quality assurance, law regulations	Accreditation of projects and quality assurance	Private funding	Competitors and local regulations	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	12-36 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + Corporations Products, processes, market	Low flexibility Stablish plans and project	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/ Universities/ Associations Basic Research and Dissemination	Medium flexibility They are based on scientific evidences, they generate scientific knowledge	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to be more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes) and dissemination of those	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Technological centers Applied research	Medium flexibility Competitive improvement of companies and their contribution to economic development	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in. They search for new ideas in research centers

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the private funding is well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, they will comply with the rules and goals even if they are not the partner that is developing a project or a task because the whole project is considered as a single result.

Case 11: Collaboration Italy/Israel

Name of the food systems co-creation case /Country: Italy/Israel

One or two key features: Hydroponics

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): On going

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The letter of intent (Memorandum of Understanding, MoU) for facilitating high-tech innovations for agricultural crops is a signed agreement between the State of Israel, its Embassy in Italy and Confagricoltura.

Which ambitions and objectives: The primary goal is to produce more with fewer natural resources, through solutions that promote the achievement of EU objectives of the Green New Deal and the contrast to the consequences of climate change.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Collaboration relationships continue between the Israeli Embassy in Italy and Confagricoltura in the name of scientific research and technological innovation, bringing together research and entrepreneurial activity in agriculture.

What external input and output: seven priorities: growing indoors, hydroponics, vertical agriculture, geponics, aeroponics, innovative greenhouses, organic fertilization solutions to Confagricoltura companies.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Israel - Italy Hydroponic	Confagricoltura	Soilless cultivation	Avoiding fungal diseases	MoU between partners	Advanced Israeli know how for Confagricoltura	2020 on going
geponics	Tap	Micro irrigation	Avoiding damage from alien insects			
aeroponics	Vertical Field					
Vertical agri	Growponics					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Israel is a leader in soilless cultivation and microirrigation	Openness to new production methods, green transition	On the occasion of Ecomondo Digital, the Embassy of Israel and the organization of agricultural Entrepreneurs with the support of the Israeli Export Institute have promoted a meeting on innovations	-Scientific research -Technological innovation development -Addressing water shortage	Tap Vertical Fields Growponics Agam and Mapal
	Collaborative approaches			

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The partnership constitutes an extremely important occasion to present the technologies developed in Israel to address the ecological transition.

Case 12: OSAF (Observatory on Smart Agri-Food), Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Italy

One or two key features: Agriculture 4.0

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): On going

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The research contract for facilitating the growth and innovation in the agri-food system (Agriculture 4.0) is a signed agreement between Enapra/Confagricoltura, Polytechnic Institute of Milan, University of Brescia and Observatory on Smart Agri-food (OSAF). The first annual contract was signed in 2018 and is renewed every year.

Which ambitions and objectives: the main objective is to research and define strategies in order to promote innovation and digitalization in agribusiness to fine-tune the right training offerings.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Universities together with VET providers had set the partnership. The partners collaborate to understand the mechanisms of development and accompany companies in their growth.

What external input and output: Annual funding from Enapra to OSAF, themes analysis necessary for the digitalization in agribusiness, surveys on current business approaches, dissemination of questionnaires to companies.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Italy	Enapra/Conf agricoltura	Annual publication report	Workshops participation	Research contract	Dissemination to the use of incentives for digitalization in agriculture	Renewed annually
Research	OSAF	Data collection	Documents presentation			
Digitalization	Politecnico di Milano	Annual Convention on March	Working tables			
Start up	Università di Brescia					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Link between research and training providers	Interdisciplinarity	Agrifood companies	Agriculture 4.0 data collection	Annual meetings
Synergy		VET providers		
		Universities		

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The partnership stimulates all the participants to collaborate and to search or create innovation in the agri-food business, beneficial to right training offerings.

Main sources: <https://www.osservatori.net/en/research/active-observatories/smart-agrifood>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPaths; WP4

Case 13: Hubfarm, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Italy

One or two key features: Digitalisation

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): On going

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The agreement was created with the objective of accompanying agricultural enterprises towards technological, digital and ecological transition. It establishes a partnership between Confagricoltura, Microsoft Italia and Reale Mutua.

Which ambitions and objectives: Supporting agricultural producers with digital services and help companies, grappling with the ecological transition under the new CAP and the New Green Deal

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The agreement creates a common platform with developers and technology incubators, as well as with the research community, the most advanced agribusiness and technology partners.

What external input and output: Technological and digital innovations for streamlining administrative processes, certification, and high value-added digital services to foster productivity.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Italy	Confagricoltura	Data gathering and communication products	Direct contact with agricultural enterprises	Partnership Agreement	Expand access to technological tools that enable: precision farming, fertiliser use only when necessary, traceability of the supply chain	2021-ongoing
Digitalization	Microsoft Italia	Cloud platform	Provide digital tools		Innovate the Italian agricultural sector, and make it competitive	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Science based solutions	Reciprocal cooperation, through the adoption of mutually beneficial tools	Agricultural enterprises are clustered through the platform and create a network that enables them to access digital tools more easily and to grow	Innovation in agriculture	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Thanks to HubFarm, it will be possible to achieve economic sustainability together with environmental sustainability, to meet the challenge of producing more with less.

Main sources: <https://www.confagricoltura.it/ita/network-confagricoltura/sistema-confagricoltura/hubfarm>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPaths WP4

foodpaths

Case 14: ACTIA, France

Association de coordination technique pour l'industrie agro-alimentaire (ACTIA) / FRANCE

The French network of technical institutes of the agri-food industry/ Running structure

Source: <https://www.actia-asso.eu/presentation/>

Evolution

Association de coordination technique pour l'industrie agro-alimentaire/Technical Coordination Association for the Food Industry

National coordination structure, Actia federates the activities of the technical institutes of the agro-food industry, as well as the partner centres, interface and technical, whose 1200 researchers, engineers and technicians accompany companies, in particular SMEs, on a daily basis.

With more than 80 sites in France, the Actia Centres intervene in all sectors of the food industry, as well as on non-food valuations of agricultural products (biotechnology, fine chemistry, cosmetics, pharmacy).

Actia dynamizes and catalyzes this unique network of development, transfer, information and training by making play in synergy the know-how and the complementarities of each. By its missions of incitement, coordination and communication, Actia is an essential element of the food-processing world.

For its missions, directed by its board of directors, Actia benefits from the expertise of its scientific and technical council.

Recognized by the ministry in charge of Agro-alimentary, as operator of the State, Actia benefits from its active support to develop its activities, within the framework of its contract of objectives.

A stronger partnership between public laboratories and technical institutes

The joint technological unit (UMT) is a partnership tool between a technical institute and a public research unit, set up and supported by the Ministry of Agri-food. For the agri-food sector, Actia coordinates fourteen UMTs with complementary themes between them and with those of the RMTs.

A national centre of competence

On its theme, the UMT allows to propose a unique and recognized entry in research and development for its various professional, industrial, research and public interlocutors.

A unique and innovative technological research tool...

Like the joint research unit, the UMT encourages synergies between researchers and engineers through the specific features of its operation: unity of location and management, co-construction of the scientific programme with a national vocation, pooling of technical and human resources, mixed and complementary skills.

And expertise and transfer to companies

Translating the expectations of professionals into research problems, the UMT is dedicated to technological research, the results of which are operational and can be applied in the short and medium term. Its technical advances are disseminated so that they can be used and applied rapidly and to the best advantage by all operators.

Case 15: TKI (Top Sector Agrifood), the Netherlands

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: **TOP SECTOR AGRIFOOD / TKI**

One or two key features: **Innovation platform (cluster) for The Netherlands food industry**

Source: <https://topsectoragrifood.nl/>

Status: **Running initiative (X-Present)**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Top Sector Agri & Food is one of the 9 top sectors in which the Netherlands excels worldwide. The business community, universities, research centres, governments and civil society organizations are working together on knowledge and innovation, internationalization, human capital and reducing regulatory pressure to make this position even stronger..

Which ambitions and objectives: The Agri & Food Top Sector stimulates new knowledge and innovations, primarily by setting up and financing research and innovation projects. This not only involves fundamental and applied research, but also valorisation.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Final responsibility for Top Sector Agri & Food rests with the Top Team, which is composed of representatives from the business community, science and government (the 'golden triangle'). The Top Team forms the day-to-day management and is chaired by a figurehead from the sector.

What external input and output: The Netherlands faces challenges in the fields of agriculture, water and food. Our food production system must therefore be converted in the coming years into a system that works climate neutrally, reuses raw materials, has no negative impact on the environment and offers space for biodiversity. At the same time, the consumption of healthy and sustainable food must be stimulated, food waste must be further combated and work must be done on the appreciation of food and greenery, while good revenue models for the entire chain, including the farmer and market gardener, remain important. The knowledge and innovation agenda consists of the following missions: Circular agriculture, Climate neutral agriculture and food production, Climate-proof rural and urban areas, Valued, healthy and safe food, Sustainable and safe North Sea and other waters, The Netherlands is and will remain the best protected and liveable delta, Key Technologies

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
The Netherlands (national)	Food industry	Strategic Research and Innovation agenda	Network	National (The Netherlands)	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	X-Present
Innovation and business	Funders	Network	Cooperation initiatives	Language (Dutch, English)	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and env).	Project setting of actions
Industry including SMEs	Universities and research centres	Living-lab	Innovation Resources		Innovation	
	Government (Ministries)	Projects / Funding	Competitiveness		Think-Tank	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Cluster of ministry, knowledge suppliers and industry	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for the Netherlands	NFTPs platform, National network
Innovation	Resource facilitation			
Funding				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Main sources: **Top Sector Agrifood (TKI)**

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP4

Case 16: Pôle Vitagora, France

Pôle Vitagora/ FRANCE

The leading food and well being innovation cluster / Running initiative

Source: <https://www.vitagora.com/en>

Presentation & Competencies

Created in 2005, Vitagora is an innovation cluster uniting a membership of agri-food businesses with public or private knowledge providers and developers of innovative solutions. Today Vitagora provide its members with a range of tools and services helping to enrich and accelerate their agile innovation processes and to attain their development goals.

Since Vitagora's regional beginnings, we have built a dynamic innovation ecosystem of industry professionals: over 550 businesses (startups, SMEs, multinationals etc.), public or private research units, and partner organisations, throughout France and abroad.

Together, we work to produce a tasty, healthy and sustainable food product and service offer, driven by the demands of today's consumers, ever more concerned with the impact of food on their wellbeing.

Since 2015, Vitagora holds the Gold Label of Cluster Management excellence for its actions in guiding industry innovation – **further faster. Together.**

- > **Vitagora's events and individual business connections** help the food companies to identify and meet their future clients in France and abroad.
 - > **Vitagora's communication channels and events** promote the food companies' solutions to its whole ecosystem.

 - > **Vitagora helps the food companies to evaluate the market potential of your solution:** strategic mapping and analysis of competitors and B2B opportunities in markets around the world.
 - > **Vitagora provides the food companies with individual expert support** to access your target markets faster and in managing the risks.
 - > **Vitagora identifies innovation or research project opportunities** in France and Europe.
 - > **Vitagora's experienced team of project engineers guides you in the set-up of your innovation projects:** partner search, IP management, funding search etc.
 - > **Vitagora's "Europe Watch" team provides specific guidance** to optimise your chances of success during European Commission project calls.
 - > **Vitagora organises partnering missions to other countries** to help you promote your expertise and solutions.
 - > **Vitagora provides individual support** to boost French food companies international development: diagnostics, actions plans, partner search etc.
- Vitagora provides a range of practical services and tools to address the daily challenges of running a business. Included in the membership are practical services covering the following areas:
- > **All business sectors:** Human resources, Strategy and finances, Regulatory affairs, Intellectual property...
 - > **Specific to the Agri-food sector:** Quality assurance, Production & logistics, Export...

Case 17: Milan Food Policy, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Food Policy / Italy

One or two key features: health and sustainable food system

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Food Policy is the city's food policy. It represents one of the legacies of Expo 2015, and is a support tool for city government promoted in synergy by the Municipality of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation to make the Milanese food system more sustainable

Which ambitions and objectives: 1. ensure healthy food for all 2. promote the sustainability of the food system 3. educate about food 4. fight against waste 5. scientific research

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: the Milan Food Policy was launched in 2015 and gradually entered the municipality governance moving from an office in the municipality to become a direction

What external input and output:

An illustration

(Product, service, organisation change, ...)

https://youtu.be/tr_vCYQh1LU?list=PLHd5UJ5aE67pcy59XCbPTFrleQmndwgxK

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diet	Milan Municipality, NGOs, Foundations, Researchers, civil society	Projects, new policies and regulations		Support from the Milan Municipality Governance and of Cariplo Foundation as neutral actor	New projects, new local hubs, new regulations and new policies	Actions can last from few months up to many years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The main strength of the Milan Food Policy lies in long term engagement of the Milan Municipality and Cariplo Foundation	The Milan Food Policy can not be considered a flexible actor but it enjoys Cariplo Foundation's flexibility while can benefit from the strategic relevance of the Milan Municipality	The main strength of the Milan Food Policy lies in the ability to create connections between all actors of the Milan Urban Food System	Cariplo Foundation and Milan Municipality jointly define their goals every years	Milan Food Policy interacts with other Municipalities all over the world to share and transfer local best practices on sustainable food system

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The fact that the Milan Municipality has a dedicated direction for the local food policy makes this practice extremely resilient and sustainable.

Main sources: <https://foodpolicymilano.org/en/objectives-and-priorities/>

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Case 18: Milan Food Waste Hub, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

Milan Food Waste Hubs/ Italy

One or two key features:food waste and innovative way of recovering food

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):running.....

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: in 2016 the Municipality of Milan, Assolombarda and Politecnico di Milano, shared "Zero Sprechi" memorandum of understanding, with the aim of reducing food waste and innovating the ways of recovering food for the people in need, designing and experimenting a model of collection and redistribution of food surplus, based on local neighborhood networks

Which ambitions and objectives: One of the priorities of Milan Food Policy is reducing food waste by engaging different local actors such as institutions, research centers, private sector, foundations and social actors

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: . The actions started between 2018 and 2019 with the launching of a first pilot project in Municipio 9 and in 2021 there are 3 more Hubs in other city neighborhoods

What external input and output:

An illustration

(Product, service, organisation change, ...)

<https://youtu.be/5vOYYBN4G4U>

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food waste	institutions, research centers, private sector, foundations and social actors	New hubs,		It requires the support of a charity	New hubs	Actions can last from 12 months up to many years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Food Waste Hubs model allow the mixing of recovered food, making it possible to donate a varied, nutritious and balanced food offer to people in need, alongside the direct contact between the supermarket and the non-profit organization		The main strength of the Food Waste Hubs lies in the ability to create connections and engaging different local actors	Municipality of Milan, Assolombarda and Politecnico di Milano jointly define their goals	In order to have success and improve they need to create local networks (different types of stakeholders from NGOs, to private organizations and public institutions)

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The Municipality of Milan, with Food Waste Hubs, is the winner, for the category "Build a waste free World", of the first edition of the Earthshot Prize, a prestigious international award on the best solutions to protect the environment, launched by Prince William and the Royal Foundation

Main sources: <https://foodpolicymilano.org/en/food-waste-hubs/>

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Case 19: MiRi, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country
 One or two key features:
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:
 Which ambitions and objectives:
 Evolution of their governance model and organisation:
 What external input and output:

An illustration
 (Product, service, organisation change, ...)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
MiRi supports the schools everyday delivering healthy and sustainable foods to children, teachers and old people.	They are a flexible actor as they are able to develop different diets according to the specific requirements (ethical and religious as well as dependent from healthy issues).	They interact with Milan Municipality as well as parents and the different schools they reach every day.	The goals are decided together with the Milan Municipality and more specifically the Food Policy Area	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Main sources:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WUUC0mJgcT09UJkw7CpaVsXbH-CtbfID/view>

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Case 20: PLANET, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Italy, Austria, France and the Netherlands

One or two key features: Training on Agroenergy

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): stopped

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: PLANET project is based on the agreement between multiple actors, including Confagricoltura and the University of Turin, which is the project's coordinator.

Which ambitions and objectives: The goal of the project is to provide innovative training to farmers who own RES plants or want to invest, with practical and ICT skills in a work-based environment related to the daily management of the plant.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The initiative was developed thanks the efforts of the Department of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Sciences of the University of Turin and Confagricoltura, to respond to the training needs of agricultural entrepreneurs in the daily management and efficiency of renewable energy plants, involving, besides Italy, Austria, France and the Netherlands as well.

What external input and output: 4 modules available through the open learning platform which last 18 weeks (10 weeks on-line, 4 weeks in-class, 4 weeks work-based)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Education	UNITO, AERES, AGRAR+	Learning modules and training platforms	Development of course material for practical training	MoU between partners involved	update farmers and plant operators	2019-2020
RES plant management	Farmers willing to invest in RES; Owners of RES plant; Students increasing their employability	RES plant	Attending courses and lessons		make efficient, sustainable and profitable renewable energy production on farms	
Dissemination	Confagricoltura	Communication material	Outreach and Circulation on information		Engaging stakeholders and nurturing awareness about the existing opportunities through this project	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
management and maintenance skills	Interdisciplinarity	actors create a network with each other in which to develop peer to peer learning experiences and also multi-stakeholder exchanges	Continuous training of farmers on the sources of renewable energy and plant management	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Through constant farmers training and upgrades, agriculture can remain a competitive sector capable of providing clean energy and respecting natural planetary boundaries

Main sources: <https://www.confagricoltura.it/eng/european-projects/planet>

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Case 21: Reinwaste, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: MED Region

One or two key features: Waste management and prevention

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): stopped

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The agreement has been set between Confagricoltura and Agencia de Gestión Agraria y Pesquera de Andalucía (AGAPA) (Agency for the management of agriculture and fisheries of Andalusia) within the framework of the European Union-sponsored REINWASTE project.

Which ambitions and objectives: Improving resource use efficiency along the food value chain, without compromising food security

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The agreement was created in order to implement the REINWASTE Project, which is co-funded by the Interreg MED transnational Cooperation Programme and European Regional Development Fund to promote the Mediterranean innovation capacities and the development of smart and sustainable growth.

What external input and output: Funding from Interreg MED transnational Cooperation Programme and European Regional Development Fund. The output foster the effective technology transfer, by a collaborative&open innovation approach, among agrofood clusters, R&D centres and agriculture and agrofood companies from the regions involved in Reinwaste (Emilia-Romagna, Andalusia, PACA) for zero inorganic waste.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
MED Region	Pool of agri-food companies (agro-food business associations, food companies and farmers)	pilot projects to test "on-the-spot"	Overcome the persistent lack of knowledge on the Best Available Technologies and the diversity and fragmentation of waste prevention procedures	Interreg MED transnational Cooperation Programme	Transferability Plans to other Agrifood & Agriculture supply chains and Protocols for sustainable management of waste for transference purposes	February 2018-January 2021
R&I	Pool of experts (R&I centres and clusters)	Sustainability Analysis, Market Analysis and Feasibility Study	identifying available solutions		adoption of best available pilot solutions for the reference sectors	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Managerial and technological skills and knowledge to uptake innovative solutions and create waste prevention procedures	Partners share a joint vision to face the challenge: finding and testing the best-advanced solutions in inorganic waste	several SMEs from the Agrofood sector through their national Federations together with Technology Transfer centers, innovative Clusters	Implement specific pilot projects to test "on-the-spot" to achieve zero inorganic waste	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Through the creation of the aforementioned partnership, concrete and scalable solutions to mitigate the environmental impact of the supply chain have been identified, encouraging the use of more sustainable alternative strategies in order to reduce waste at the regional level.

Main sources: <https://www.confagricoltura.it/eng/european-projects/reinwaste>

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Case 22: Mountain and Rural Areas Protocol, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Italy

One or two key features: Restart from villages

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): ongoing partnership

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The agreement between Confagricoltura, Unione Nazionale Comuni ed Enti Montani (UNCCEM) Legambiente and Federparchi promotes local tourism and reorganisation of inland areas. The agreement has been signed in 2020.

Which ambitions and objectives: The goal is to revitalize and promote the country's inland and rural areas, which constitute cultural heritage and a magnet for tourism

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Confagricoltura with national organizations (Unione Nazionale Comuni ed Enti Montani - UNCCEM) as well as environmental association that gather and represent mountain municipalities and mountain communities, consortia, chambers of commerce and other entities operating in the mountains had set this partnership in support of local and rural land protection historic houses safeguard.

What external input and output: The project aims to

- 1) Preserve, manage and promote rural territories in order to ensure social cohesion and environmental sustainability
- 2) Bring economic benefits to farmers and workers in the area, through the rehabilitation of these districts
- 3) Providing employment opportunities for women and youth, key pillars of rural communities

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Italian rural landscape	Confagricoltura	Promotion of Local agri-food products	Enhancement of agricultural and forestry business and strengthening existing agricultural, livestock and forestry supply chains	MoU between partners	Enhance productive activities, improving the quality, sustainability of production, and profitability of local businesses and communities	2020-ongoing
Mountain and Apennine areas	Environmental association	The forest resource and wood-energy supply chain	Create awareness of the potential of given areas		counteract local people's distress and curb depopulation phenomena	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Dissemination of information to enhance marginalized areas and arrange their reorganization	The actors adapt to each other with common strategies and complementary actions, as the impact on the territory with significant effects on the economic, social and environmental dimensions	Partners form an alliance to achieve the above results	Making local areas attractive, promoting tourism and strengthening the agricultural value chain	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

This agreement promotes the following aspects such as: sustainable forest management, promotion of characteristic mountain productions, protection of landscape and rural land, protection of biodiversity, prevention and management of environmental risks.

Main sources:

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP4

Case 23: AGRicoltura 100, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country **AGRIcultura 100 / Italy ...AGRICOLTURA 100**.....

One or two key features: **Enhance the contribution of agriculture to the sustainable growth of the country**

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): **Running 2020 - on going**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: AGRicoltura100 is the initiative promoted by Reale Mutua Assicurazioni and Confagricoltura with the patronage of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies and the Ministry of Ecological Transition, to enhance the contribution of agriculture to sustainability and its role in the new recovery phase. It started in 2020 and was renewed in 2022 and 2023.

Which ambitions and objectives: The survey aims to prepare an annual report: The contribution of agriculture to the sustainability of the country, which will be presented in a public event, with participation of the institutions and companies awarded for their initiatives of sustainability.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Confagricoltura and Reale Mutua create a double survey (online and by phone) to analyse the sustainability of the agricultural firms that participate. The firms participate to win the prizes of sustainability, the survey become an important tool for the govern to know the national situation about the sustainability.

What external input and output: AGR100 promotes the value of sustainability e supports the commitment of businesses to:

- be more competitive and more capable of respond to consumer expectations
- improve the social and environmental impact
- innovate production processes and implement more performing initiatives.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Rural Italy	Farmers	Survey about sustainability	environmental impact	Governance of sustainability	impact on the territory	Annual 2020 – 2022 – 2023
Farms	Confagricoltura	Report about situation of sustainability	food quality		social cohesion in the country	
	Reale Mutua				generates value	
	Ministry of Agriculture					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network of farmers		Farmers fulfil the survey		
Statistical analysis		Confagri and Reale Mutua give prizes and write the report		

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Exchange of know-how and good practices, badge for sustainable farms, national impact on sustainable behaviour. It has an impact on the territory and on the environmental balance but also on the health and well-being of people, as guarantor of the origin of the quality of food production.

Main sources: <https://www.agricolturasostenibile.eu/>

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Case 24: Ecotrophelia, France

Ecotrophelia Europe / FRANCE

The Student Awards of Food Innovation / Running initiative

Source: <https://eu.ecotrophelia.org/>

Presentation & History

ECOTROPHELIA has the ambition to promote entrepreneurship and competitiveness within the European food industry by implementing a training network of excellence in food innovation and the organization of national and European food innovation competitions "**The Student Awards of Food Innovation**" a real eye-opener for the food industry. ECOTROPHELIA is a great platform for innovation and inspiration for the food industry. It allows capitalizing on the limitless creativity and energy of our brightest and most enterprising students, supported by the best Universities and High Education Institutes.

The competition is a major catalyst:

- offering students full-scale learning and training, by confronting them with real situations, the rules and laws of an uncompromising market in a state of perpetual evolution.
- developing a culture of curriculum innovation, by making changes to teaching methods, particularly through project-based learning, in direct contact with professionals in the sector.

ECOTROPHELIA is a "**real ideas**" incubator for the food industry, it is an age-group marker on the consumption trends of the millennial generation.

Established in France in 2000, **ECOTROPHELIA** expanded to a European scale in 2008, ECOTROPHELIA Europe is organized by the European Technology Platform "**Food for Life**", ANIA (*National Association of Food Industries*) and CCI Vaucluse. On the principle of a food innovation "Champions League" each European country organizes its own national competition to select the most innovative food project that will then be presented at **ECOTROPHELIA Europe**. Each country selection is coordinated by its national food federation. The teams are composed of 2 to 10 students from either public or private higher education European establishments, scientific or commercial.

Key-dates of the competition:

2008 - First ECOTROPHELIA Europe session with 8 food federations (*Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia and Spain*)

2011 - The European Commission recognized the exemplary nature of TROPHELIA and gave the go-ahead to the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vaucluse to implement a European project for the promotion of eco-innovation in the food industry sector: ECOTROFOOD. The competition TROPHELIA then became ECOTROPHELIA

2014 - ECOTROPHELIA inspired the creation of FOODLAB, a European Laboratory of food innovations to encourage entrepreneurship in higher education and promote student entrepreneurship, supported by the European Union in the context of the ERASMUS programme.

2015 - ECOTROPHELIA Europe 2015 took place at the Universal Exhibition Milan 2015 whose theme was "Feeding the Planet, Energy for Life". Based on a Champion's League of food innovation, 16 European countries participate in ECOTROPHELIA Europe 2015 in the European Commission Pavilion.

2019 - ECOTROPHELIA promoted the development of a Strategic Partnership project in the scope of the ERASMUS+ program - FEEDtheMIND, which brings together 7 partners from 5 European countries to work on new pedagogical methods on knowledge and skills acquisition. Beyond the competitions, ECOTROPHELIA has become a network of training excellence in food innovation that mobilises higher education institutions and national federations of food industries in Europe. Thus, the ECOTROPHELIA network, a reference educational model supported by the European Union, plays an organisational role in promoting innovation and entrepreneurship among students.

PRODUCTS DATABASE

PRIZE WINNERS

BOOKS

PRESS

TEAMS

VIDEOS

Case 25: Food Science Festival, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Food&Science Festival / Italy ...**FOOD SCIENCE FESTIVAL**.....

One or two key features: **A place for discussion, fun, training and interaction where, through food, we can discover and perceive the future that awaits us.**

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): 2018 – on going

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Food & Science Festival is a unique scientific dissemination event of national and international importance that tackles and explores issues related to the science of food production and consumption in a creative and accessible way. Born in 2018, it has reached its fifth edition.

Which ambitions and objectives: The Food & Science Festival, in addition to offering farmers an unmissable opportunity to update and share information and experiences, is an event created to satisfy an audience of onlookers of all ages who want to get to know and experience innovation, stories and the challenges facing the food and agri-food sector.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Promoted by Confagricoltura Mantova, conceived by FRAME and organized by Mantova Agricola, with the patronage of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies, the Ministry of the Environment and Land and Sea Protection, the Lombardy Region, the Municipality of Mantua and the Chamber of Commerce of Mantua as institutional partners.

What external input and output: Students are privileged interlocutors for the Festival and, in order to give young people the necessary tools to make informed choices on issues related to the production and consumption of food, it is strategic to stimulate their curiosity towards scientific research on these issues and involve them in the Festival in different ways:

- a rich program of meetings, laboratory activities and exhibition itineraries dedicated to schools of all levels during the three days of the event;
- events that actively involve Technical and Professional Institutes that deal with the production and consumption of food;
- school-work alternation projects that enhance the personal inclinations of each student and create, through active participation, the best conditions for effective learning.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Italy	Confagricoltura	Science of food production	Food innovations show on		Share of knowledge	Annual 2018 – on going
	Farmers				Education	
	Innovators				Innovation	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Innovation knowledge		Sharing knowledge		Economic growth

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The festival allows citizens, students and other producers to know the possibilities of innovation of the food system. It generates economic growth in the area as well as ensuring the possibility of mutual collaboration between realities that had not had the opportunity to know each other previously.

Main sources: <https://www.foodsciencefestival.it/>

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Case 26: PTEPA (Spanish Technological Platform of Fishing and Aquaculture), Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Spanish Technological Platform of Fishing and Aquaculture - Living lab / Spain (PTEPA)

One or two key features: Technological Platform

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: After 2 years of study and organization, at the end of 2007, the operating council representative of the sector was selected and began work with the support of the Secretary General of Maritime Fishery (also known as the Secretary General of Fishery). In their first “official meeting”, with entities that now form the Board of Directors, they established the Platform’s Plan of Action. Since then PTEPA has become the primary hub for all agents involved in R&D&I in the Fishing and Aquaculture.

Which ambitions and objectives: PTEPA is a non-profit organization aiming at promoting technological development and innovation in the fishery and aquaculture sector, including processing and commercialization. The objective is to unify interested parties of the sector by coordinating actions and sharing information related to new technologies.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: The Spanish Technological Platform of Fishing and Aquaculture (PTEPA) is a non-profit association supported by the Secretary General of Fishery. Their structure divides in **Technical Work Groups** (They analyse and study the current situation to decide the strategic plans to follow, based on new technological challenges), **General Assembly** (The governing body of the platform), **Board of Directors** (In charge of coordinating the actions of the Platform to achieve the objectives), **Representatives Group** (They create a coordination plan for positioning internationally and nationally), **Consulting Group** (Coordinate different administrative groups in Spain), **Financial Group** (financial measures to achieve the objectives established) and **Technical Secretary** (Support the Working Groups, members and other management actors).

What external input and output: The PTEPA covers the whole value chain in fishery and aquaculture in 6 strategic lines of working. Marine living resources, Fishery Technologies, Aquaculture, Transformation Technologies and Commercialisation.

Pic 1. Current governance model and organization

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Better Products	Research Centers	Resources	Identify technological challenges	Public/private funding	Laws, competitors	More sustainable products and better efficiency	12-36 months
New processes and techniques	Technological Centers, Working groups	Sustainable fishing system	Identify technological interests to enhance collaborations	Public/private funding	Laws, competitors	More sustainable processes (less impact and waste)	12-36 months
competitivity / diffusion	Partners, Auxiliar firms, Group of Representatives, Technical Secretary	Promotion activities, Discussion forums, Promotional events	Identify possible new partners to start projects	Private funding	Competitors and prices	More sustainable final products (packaging), Competitive products	12-18 months
Regulations	Regulatory Council, Organisations, Federations, Administration	Quality assurance, Certification of products	Qualified personnel to assess and figure out weaknesses	Authorities	Food Security laws	Quality but sustainable products	12-36 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Corporation/ Auxiliar firms/ Federations Big fish commercial net with big offer of products	High flexibility They follow the company objectives after the new technologies are delivered by research centers	They usually become clusters or support developing projects	They usually try to focus on technology goals but they slightly depend on external regulations	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/ I+D specialized of big capacity, Great nutritional value, Excellent technological know-how.	Low flexibility They are based on scientific evidences and financing	They usually become partners in R&D/ sustainability projects	They try to be more focus on technology (applied to both product and processes) goals but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Big Companies Lead internationally, compromised with sustainability	Medium flexibility They depend on market trends	They usually become partners in R&D/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in. They search for new ideas in research centers

Some words about the sustainability behavior of actors

PTEPA tries to go toward a sustainable use of marine resources. The sustainable fishery product certification is implemented and there is some work about developing a more sustainable fishing system through the optimization of fishery processes.

In the area of R&D&I they focus on creating new points of view, more practical and sustainable that could achieve social changes and environmental improvements.

Case 27: PTV (Wine Technology Platform), Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Wine Technology Platform – Living Lab / Spain (PTV)

One or two key features: Technological Platform

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: Since 2010 this platform emerged with the aim of promote and establish a common R&D strategy for the Spanish wine sector. Research groups, technological centers, wineries and other members of the winemaking industry needed to be coordinated in the same direction, helping eachother for progress.

The PTV has a close collaboration and synergies built with strategic organisations in the industry such as the Interprofessional Wine Organisation of Spain (OIVE), specially involved entity with which the PTV has collaborated since 2018 through a joint action plan, the Spanish Wine Federation (FEV), the Spanish Wine Market Observatory (OeMV) or, at the European level, the European Committee of Wine Companies (CEEV).

Which ambitions and objectives: An unstructured sector with enough investment but bad optimization on resources was in need of a solid structure that integrated all the actors on viticultural panorama. Thus, the main objective of PTV is to create a common strategy for the Spanish wine sector in order to increase the quality, competitiveness, posicioning and efficiency of a group that has a lot of resources and good conditions to grow.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: The Wine Technology Platform (PTV) Association of Spain is a nonprofit public-private association supported by the Ministry of Science and Innovation and by the State Research Agency. The consolidation of its organisational and operational structure, was pushed through direct financial aid from the Support Programme for Spanish Technology Platforms and ongoing financial support so that its members can design and implement their R&D&I projects through different tools offered by the State Plan for Scientific and Technical Research and Innovation.

What external input and output: With the third edition of SIA (Strategic Innovation Agenda) of the Wine Industry, 28 strategic lines were established and clustered in 6 working areas in PTV taking into account every actor in the value chain of wine.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
				Rules	& Incentives)		
New products	Universities, Research Centers	Drink products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products and positive effects in health	12-36 months
New processes and techniques	Wineries, Technological Centers	Drink products and winemaking tools	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (energy, waste treatments)	12-36 months
Posicioning/competitivy	Partners, Auxiliar firms	Promotion activities	Projects (consortia)	Market	Competitors and prices	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	6-24 months
Better processes	Regulatory Council, Wine Organisations, Federations, Administration	Quality assurance	Acreditation	Market	Competitor sand prices	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	6-24 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Partners/ Corporation/ Auxiliar firms Products, processes, market	High flexibility Willingness to be applied to their products/processes	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/ Universities Basic Research	Low flexibility They are based on scientific evidences and market behaviour	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to be more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes) goals but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in. Also with the wineries.
Wineries/ Technological centers Applied research and try new tools	Medium flexibility Intermediate scale to test different technologies	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in. They search for new ideas in research centers

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

Wineries, auxiliary industries, researchers and managers are all working together to build an industry that – aware of its own needs and problems – uses R&D&I to find solutions, propose alternatives and drive sustainability, digitalization and reindustrialisation. It is in the area of R&D&I where the PTV plays a crucial role. It plays and will play an increasingly relevant role in the close ties that the wine industry has with sustainability and the fight against climate change.

Case 28: Go Vitinnat, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: GO VITINNAT – Living Lab / Spain

One or two key features: Operational Group

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: The Program for Rural Development 2014-2020 in Spain consists of a National Framework, seventeen Regional Programs and a National Program. One of the points treated on this program, is focused on the creation of supra-autonomous operational groups. As a result of this, the Operational Group (O.G) "VITINNAT" was born, becoming part of the European Association for Innovation in terms of agricultural productivity and sustainability.

Which ambitions and objectives: The O.G. VITINNAT focuses on solving one of the biggest problems that currently affects in grapevine cultivation: wood diseases. For this, they developed two complementary strategies: A new zero and stable waste product whose active ingredients will come from agro-industrial waste (some recovered by BODEGA MATARROMERA from its by-products, representing a clear example of circular economy); and new ozone technologies to control soil-borne wood diseases.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: The Operational Groups are key elements in the development of the European Innovation Partnership in productive and sustainable agriculture. They are groups of actors with different profiles, such as farmers, ranchers, foresters, agri-food or forestry industries, public or private R&D&i or training and advisory centers, technology centers or non-profit institutions, among others.

What external input and output: VITINNAT is formed by benefactors (CTAEX, Bodegas Matarromera, IDAI Nature, AGROZONO and Health Institute Carlos III) and also collaborators (Regulatory Council D.O. Ribera del Duero, Wine Technology Platform, Spanish Society of Organic Agriculture and CICTEX).

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a *GAME*):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
New products	Universities, Research Centers	More sustainability, innovative and efficient products	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products and positive effects in health	12-36 months
New processes and techniques	Technological Centers and Research centers	More sustainability, innovative and efficient techniques	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (energy, waste treatments)	12-36 months
Representation/ Implementation of innovation plans	Partners, Companies, Federations, Associations	Promotion activities, financing, Interactive sessions know-how	Support of created projects	Private funding	Competitors and prices	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	12-18 months
Administration and regulation	Regulatory Council, Organisations, Federations, Administration	Quality assurance, law regulations	Accreditation of projects and quality assurance	Private funding	Competitors and local regulations	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	12-36 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + Corporations Products, processes, market	Low flexibility Stablish plans and project	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/ Universities/ Associations Basic Research and Dissemination	Medium flexibility They are based on scientific evidences, they generate scientific knowledge	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to be more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes) and dissemination of those	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Technological centers Applied research	Medium flexibility Competitive improvement of companies and their contribution to economic development	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in. They search for new ideas in research centers

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the private funding is well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, they will comply with the rules and goals even if they are not the partner that is developing a project or a task because the whole project is considered as a single result.

Case 29: SRIP HRANA (Research and innovation partnership for sustainable food systems), Slovenia

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: SRIP HRANA / Slovenia

One or two key features: Research and Innovation partnership for Sustainable Food Production

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The partnership was co-created in 2016. Several key actors are involved: agriculture holdings, companies, cooperatives, research institutions, national authorities and other interested parties

Which ambitions and objectives: becoming the main national contact point for companies and research institutions to promote networking and cooperation of ambitious and development-oriented parties in the area of agriculture, food science technology, as well as nutrition and other related areas.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: 5 sectorial value chains (wheat, fruit, meat, milk and beer production), 3 horizontal activities (human resources, digitalization, internationalization) and sensory analysis

What external input and output: dialogue with governmental and non-governmental bodies

The key activities that the partnership offers to the members are based on networking, exchange of good practices, organization of professional events, assistance to individual partners who are looking for cooperation opportunities within and outside the SRIP HRANA partnership, the organization of professional and business delegations and visits, and last but not least, the partnership is also the contact point for every other stakeholder who sees the importance of connecting for the purposes of development and innovation breakthrough. In relation to the state and governmental and non-governmental bodies, SRIP HRANA plays an important role as a credible and representative counterpart in the preparation and formulation of the state's development strategies and action plans for the implementation of policies in the field of agriculture and food wines. It also has an advisory role in many areas (personnel, public ordering, agro-food development, gastronomy).

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Sustainable food innovation	agriculture holdings, companies, cooperatives, research institutions, national authorities	New connections, sustainable innovation, business delegations, development of the agrifood sector	Organization of networking and professional events, connecting to european sectoral associations, working with experts in other fields		Sustainable innovation in Slovenian agrifood industry	2016 -

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Producing and selling a food product	Yes, according to market and new research	Yes, food association	yes	yes
Fundamental and applied research	Yes, according to current and future needs	no	yes	yes

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The actors are highly motivated to take actions within the partnership. They give initiatives and proposals for new activities or upgrade of existing activities. Activities within the partnership are co-created with the members and therefore also supported by them. Many sectors are aware of their responsibility and role in the transition to a sustainable food system and make important changes in the field of environment, energy, nutrition and social sustainability. Regardless of other issues, the new legislation has encouraged the members to intensify their actions in the frame of sustainability and put all aspect of sustainability first when developing a new product or making decisions as a company.

Main sources: <https://www.gzs.si/srip-hrana/>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPaths; WP4

food|paths

Funded by the European Union

Case 30: Norwegian partnership for a healthier diet, Norway

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country **NORWEGIAN PARTNERSHIP FOR A HEALTHIER DIET / Norway**

One or two key features: **Improving the diet of the Norwegian population** Source:

<https://www.helsedirektoratet.no/english/partnership-for-a-healthier-diet#organizationofthepartnership>

Status: **Running initiative (2016-2025)**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The letter of intent (Memorandum of Understanding, MoU) for facilitating a healthier diet in the population is a signed agreement between the Norwegian health authorities and food industry (food and trade organizations, food and beverage manufacturers, food retailers and food service industry). The first MoU (Norwegian, PDF) was signed on December 6th, 2016 and lasted until 31st December 2021. The partnership continues. A new and revised agreement is signed and lasts from January 1st 2022, until 31st of December 2025.

Which ambitions and objectives: There are specific goals related to reducing the intake of salt, added sugar, and saturated fat, and increasing the consumption of fruits and berries, vegetables, whole-grain foods, fish, and seafood in the population. The partners will also work for increased awareness and knowledge about health and diet by the consumers.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Health authorities together with the Food Industry (food and trade organizations, food and beverage manufacturers, food retailers and food service industry) had set the partnership. Universities and research centers collaborate on the scientific advice and the monitoring of the targets.

What external input and output: The partnership includes six priority areas: 1. Reduction of the salt content in foods and dishes, and the reduction of salt intake in the population. 2. Reduction of added sugars in foods and dishes, and the reduction of the population's intake of added sugar. 3. Reduction of saturated fat in foods and dishes, and the reduction of saturated fat intake in the population. 4. Increase the populations intake of fruits and berries, vegetables, whole grain foods and seafood by 20 percent by 2025. 5. Influence consumer behavior to increase awareness and knowledge about health and diet. 6. Monitoring of progress as specified in the agreement.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Norway	Health ministry	Products into the market	Reformulation	Memorandum of Understanding for partners	Healthier diets	2016-2025
Diet	Food industry, retail, and services	Dietary guidelines	Reaching targets on nutrient consumption	Specific targets to be monitored	Reduction of salt, sugar and saturated fats.	
Food consumption	Universities and research centres	Consumer awareness	Reduction of salt, sugar and saturated fats.			
Food reformulation	Consumer data					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Main sources: Norwegian ministry of health

Case 31: Flanders Food, Belgium

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: **FLANDERS FOOD / Belgium**

One or two key features: **Innovation platform (cluster) for the Flemish food industry**

Source: <https://www.flandersfood.com/nl>

Status: **Running initiative (2005-Present)**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Flanders' FOOD has been the innovation platform for the Flemish food industry since its foundation. Flanders' FOOD was founded in 2005 by Fevia Vlaanderen (federation of the food industry) and about 20 founding members. The premise is to gain more clout through cooperation, with each other and research partner. Currently they have more than 300 members.

Which ambitions and objectives: To strengthen competitiveness in the agri-food system, it is necessary to invest in research and innovation and between both (food) companies and social profit organizations. This across the boundaries of sectors and regions. This is the role that Flanders' FOOD, a membership organization at European level, wants to play. Everyone who sees added value in a collaboration with the ecosystem around the Flemish food industry is very welcome.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Flanders' FOOD was founded in 2005 by Fevia Vlaanderen (federation of the food industry). In 2016, an explicit choice was made to evolve into a strategy-driven innovation platform. Flanders' FOOD set up a strategic research and innovation agenda for this purpose, together with the companies from the Flemish food sector and the Flemish research institutions. Since 2018, Flanders' FOOD has been recognized as a spearhead cluster Agro-Nutrition by the Flemish government, via the innovation and entrepreneurship agency (VLAIO).

What external input and output: Flanders' FOOD is given 3 important roles by the Flemish government: 1. Central point of contact for companies, social profit organisations, knowledge institutions and governments, in the strategic domain of the Agro-food industry within the Flemish innovation system. 2. Organizing cooperation initiatives between all stakeholders of the triple helix with a view to strengthening the competitiveness of the Flemish food industry. 3. The management of specific innovation resources (earmarked project budget via VLAIO) to roll out the strategic research and innovation agenda

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Flanders (regional)	Food industry	Strategic Research and Innovation agenda	Network	Regional (Flanders)	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2005-Present
Innovation	Funders (VLAIO)	Network	Cooperation initiatives	Language (Flemish, English)	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and env).	Project setting of actions
Industry including SMEs	Universities and research centres	Living-lab	Innovation Resources		Employment / Innovation in the region	
	Regional government (Flanders)	Projects / Funding	Competitiveness			

Main sources: Flanders Food

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP4

foodpaths

Funded by the European Union

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Cluster of ministry, knowledge suppliers and industry	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for Flanders	NFTPs platform, FoodDrinkEurope platform, International outreach
Innovation	Resource facilitation			
Implementation				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Case 32: Food For Life, France

FOOD FOR LIFE FRANCE / FRANCE

Driving innovation, knowledge transfer and french competitiveness./ Running initiative (2008-2025)

Source: <https://www.ania.net/espace-pro/innovation/food-for-life-france>

Evolution

Created in 2008, Food For Life France is recognised in the French Food Industry Contract as the privileged place for building tomorrow's food R&D, Food For Life France represents a unique means of reinforcing innovation in the industry at national level, and brings together all the French R&D players: from professionals (industrialists, craftsmen, farmers, etc.) to distributors, from public research centres (INRAE, CNRS, CIRAD, IFREMER) to specialised technical centres, from competitive clusters to public authorities, including funding bodies and higher education establishments.

Food for Life France is an interface between food industry professionals, the worlds of research, training and innovation and public authorities. Its members initiate, support and structure exchanges between researchers, technical experts and companies in France. It is designated in the Food Sector Contract, signed in June 2013, as the French reference platform for food innovation. It is a tool for stimulating research and technological innovation in the food sector and thus increasing the competitiveness of the French food industry.

Its areas of intervention go beyond national borders.

In France, its missions are to :

Emerge priority thematic axes to ensure the competitiveness of the sector in a medium and long term vision, through a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. This agenda should be considered as a reference document for national actions aimed at strengthening the competitiveness of agri-food companies and increasing innovation in the food chain.

Draw up a technological roadmap setting out the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda in terms of food technology research programmes, on pre-competitive subjects with an ambition for progress, economic performance, quality and dissemination/transfer to all stakeholders. The roadmap will include a three-year work programme, a ten-year forward-looking work programme and will describe how progress will be measured.

Promote a research and innovation policy and strategy for the agri-food sector that integrates the needs of professionals in **order to direct and increase investment in these priorities and to encourage the involvement of companies in collaborative research and development programmes**. Support these priorities both at the level of public, national and regional actors and professionals.

To ensure the implementation of the actions of the **Food Sector Contract** which have been entrusted to it and the follow-up of other actions relating to the innovation theme, in order to ensure maximum impact and coherence for all the actors in the food sector.

To facilitate the capitalisation and exploitation of the results acquired by food research programmes. The objectives are the dissemination, valorisation and use of research results by food professionals (VSEs, SMEs, ETIs and GEs) as well as the promotion of existing dissemination mechanisms.

Promote the coordination of the actions of the various actors, identify good practices and **facilitate the exchange of experience** and the circulation of information.

To act as a relay for French companies to increase their participation in national and European R&D projects.

At the European level, its missions are to :

Promote the foundations and priorities of the French strategic research and innovation agenda at the level of the European Food For Life platform, as well as to the different Directorates General of the European Commission concerned directly and/or via the national thematic group.

To guide the calls for projects issued by Horizon 2020, in line with the national strategic research and innovation agenda, by defining each year the themes to be proposed and the action plan to support them as a priority. To **represent the food industry** in the pre-configuration council of the future Knowledge and Innovation Community dedicated to food (KIC Food).

Maintain close relations with national platforms in other European countries, in order to focus on the priority issues to be supported and promote them to the different European Directorates General concerned in a coordinated manner.

Contribute to developing the coordination of national responses to European calls for projects by ensuring consistency in French responses in order to make the most of synergies and avoid duplication of projects.

Encourage scientific and technological partnerships within the European Union by promoting the creation of consortia including French partners.

Case 33: Research Association of the German Food Industry, Germany

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: FEI / Germany

One or two key features: Research association of the german food industry

Source: <https://www.fei-bonn.de/en/en-index.html>

Status: Running initiative (1953-Present)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Research Association of the German Food Industry (FEI) is a non-profit, registered association supporting research projects in all fields of food science, food technology and nutritional science. About 900 companies are regularly involved in FEI. Members: Over 45 associations and federations of the industrial food sector, over 50 enterprises including the supply industry, around 120 scientific institutions and personalities of various scientific disciplines.

Which ambitions and objectives: Promotion and coordination of pre-competitive collective research projects. Currently more than 100 projects (total project volume 2020: 56,1 millions Euro).

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The FEI exists of the Executive Board, the General Assembly which vote the executive, and the Scientific Committee. The Scientific Committee is nominated by the General Assembly and the Executive Board and includes about 90 scientists from the private and public food sector proportionally.

What external input and output: The financing is provided by private funding (enterprises and industrial associations) and public funding (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action) within the programme "Industrielle Gemeinschaftsforschung (IGF)" (Industrial Collective Research for SMEs). Outcome: R&D promotion and advisory service, Contact point of industrial research for industry and science, Organisation of conferences and workshops, Edition of publications. Fields: Sponsorship of R&D activities, Applied oriented food research, Process chain: raw material – processing – consumer, Technology of the food production chain, Quality management, Technology transfer.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Network	Food industry	Research	Network	National	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	1953-Present
Innovation and research	Funders (Ministry)	Network	Cooperation initiatives	Language (German)	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and env).	Project setting of actions
Industry including SMEs	Universities and research centres	Funding	Innovation Resources		Employment / Innovation	
Funding		Projects	Competitiveness			

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Network of ministry, knowledge suppliers and industry	Funding projects, dissemination, knowledge transfer	NFTPs platform, FoodDrinkEurope platform, partners at national level
Research and innovation	Funding			
Dissemination				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Main sources: FEI

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP4

Case 34: Portugal FOODS, Portugal

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: PORTUGAL FOODS / Portugal
One or two key features: Innovation platform (cluster) for the Portuguese food industry
Source: <https://www.portugalfoods.org/en/>
Status: Running initiative (2008-Present)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Founded in 2008, PortugalFoods is a private non-profit association recognized as the national cluster for the Portuguese agrifood sector. PortugalFoods is a platform where its members establish win-win relationships with the goal of producing and sharing knowledge to support innovation, competitiveness and internationalization.

Which ambitions and objectives: PortugalFoods' mission is to boost agrifood sector competitiveness by increasing the technological index (supporting knowledge production, as well as knowledge transfer and application) and promoting the internationalization (identifying opportunities and empowering food and beverage companies in this area).

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: PortugalFoods has a membership-based governance which maintains a secretariat sustain the activities of the platform.

What external input and output: PortugalFoods acts as a network provider. It offers four main services to businesses, SMEs and knowledge suppliers: 1. Explore a portfolio of companies, products and certification suppliers. 2. Find the best match for business or knowledge transfer. 3. Share results of research and innovation. 4. Get in touch with the selected companies.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Portugal (National)	Food industry	Events	Network	National (Portugal)	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2008-Present
Innovation	Universities and research centres	Network	Collaboration – Match making	Language (Portuguese)	Projects, some in sustainable initiatives	Project setting of actions
Industry including SMEs	Certifications	Cluster structure	Innovation Resources			
Network		Projects	Competitiveness			

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Cluster of industry, attracting services and business	Goals on innovation, competitiveness and internationalization	NFTPs platform, International outreach
Innovation	Facilitation of knowledge transfer, innovation, certification, business			
Match-making within actors				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Case 35: Valorial, France

Pôle Valorial/ FRANCE

The n°1 network devoted to agri-food innovation / Running initiative

Source: <https://www.pole-valorial.fr/>

Presentation & Competencies

Making the agri-food sector of Western France the home of smarter food

Factories of the future, marketing 4.0, innovation management, new food uses, consum'actors,... with Valorial you are on the brink of a full-blown revolution!

Between "industrial operational excellence" and "better use value for the client", Valorial tackles the main challenges facing the agri-food sector against a backdrop of digital transformation and ecological transition.

Valorial's competencies:

- **Networking:** regional, national, European, international
- Consultancy services for **project set-up:** finding partners, identifying funding sources, calls for proposals, technical assessments...
- Consultancy on **innovation strategy and management:** project germination, audit of your innovation processes...
- **Stimulation and Intelligence:** Valorial' Morning, Valorial' Connection, "Sustainable agricultural production", "New technologies & operational performance in agri-agro", "Demand & supply for better eating", Focus & thematic zoom, Learning expeditions abroad, etc.
- **Project management** support
- **Promotion and communication** on your innovative projects and services: trade shows in France and abroad, media relations, etc.
- **"Augmented" services** with the members of the Partner Club: funding, digital strategy, industrial property, HR, etc.

We have opted to funnel our skills into 6 strategic areas of innovation to support businesses and researchers.

The Valorial network in numbers

390

Member

agri-food businesses & suppliers

24

Associated

thematic experts

3

Partner

Regional innovation agencies

5

Associated

foreign clusters

10

Partner Club

members

50

Member

research organisations

4

Partner

professional associations (ANIA, ABEA, ARCA, UGERIAA)

A tight-knit mesh to remove locks

Case 36: Milan Pact Award, Italy (this case has been further elaborated, case no.8 of the annex 4)

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Milan Pact Award

One or two key features: foster sustainable food systems

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors One of the most important goals of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP), is to stimulate the exchange of practices and learning between signatory cities. To foster this collaboration since 2016 the City of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation launched the Milan Pact Awards (MPA) with the aim of recognizing the most creative efforts and monitoring which cities were implementing the commitments they had made when they joined the pact. The awards are a means of encouraging action, facilitating the emergence of the best practices of the MUFPP cities, making them evident to the community with a function of inspiring the action of other signatory cities

Which ambitions and objectives: To foster the collaboration between MUFPP cities and Cariplo Foundation strength local urban food systems

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: since the beginning Cariplo Foundation and the Milan Municipality worked together on the Award

What external input and output:

<https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/award/>

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
International	Municipalities	New best practices and new food policies	Rewarding best practices	Awards (50k annually contribution + in kind engagement of local actors)	New best practices and new food policies, new signatories cities for the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact	The Award has been launched annually or every 2 years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The award represents an inspiration and a model for others grant making organization engaged on food policies . The awards represent an achievement for all municipalities active on food policies		Actors thanks to the Milan secretary interacts internationally	1. Governance 2. Sustainable diets and nutrition 3. Social and economic equity 4. food production 5. food supply and distribution 6. food waste	International collaboration across municipalities

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This activity overcome geographical differences creating a network that shares information, knowledge and best practices all around the world. During COVID pandemic this action has been extremely important as it allowed for sharing emergency answers to similar problems. In general, this action is crucial because it allow to not replicate errors fostering food system transformation all around the world in an inclusive and open way.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The practice does requires certain funding and some level of engagement and in kind contribution from the actors supporting it.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

There are more than 250 practices collected in over 6 years. I would say this is the most relevant indicator.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

For it's sustainability it requires the engagement of Cariplo Foundation and the Milan Municipality.

Main sources: <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/award/>

Case 37: SAGRI (Sustainable Agriculture), Italy/Athens

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Italy/Athens

One or two key features: Sustainable agriculture

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Ending

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Grant Agreement (GA) for facilitating high skills in the field of agro-environmental technology is a signed agreement between the Agricultural University of Athens, Confagricoltura and other partners in the EU landscapes. Sagri was a three year Erasmus+ project.

Which ambitions and objectives: The purpose was to provide farmers and agricultural stakeholders with knowledge, skills and competences in order to promote a sustainable agriculture.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Higher educational institutions and accredited training body (Universities and VET providers) had set the partnership. The project allowed agricultural workers to acquire new skills through farmers training modules.

What external input and output: analysis of skills needs, training development, development of the Open educational resources platform (OER), course delivery, evaluation

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Greece	Educational institutions	Open educational resources	Management and coordination	Grant Agreement	Acquisition of skills, Knowledge and ability	2016-2020
Portugal	Accredited training body	Course delivery, e-learning platform	Analysis of skills challenges	Specific targets to be monitored	Emphasis on environmental technologies to achieve crop sustainable production	
Italy		Pilot testing	Assessment			
Skills training		Quality assurance	Accreditation			

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Research	Cooperation	Focus group	Training seminars	Final event by INASO – PASSEGES and Agricultural University of Athens in Agrotica 2020
Innovation	Openness			
New technologies				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The project provide a wonderful opportunity to collaborate with other partners and contribute to the sustainable growth of the agricultural sector through partners cooperation and flexibility.

Main sources: <http://www.sagriproject.eu/>

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Case 38: Cultural Change 4 Inclusion, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Cultural Change / Italy **CULTURAL CHANGE 4 INCLUSION**.....

One or two key features: **Social inclusion project for refugees**.....

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): 2020 – on going

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Reale Foundation, during the period of health emergency, acknowledged the worsening of social inequalities, with particular attention to refugees present in our territory: in the face of the partnership agreement already in place with Senior - The Age of Wisdom Onlus and Confagricoltura, has devised a quality training course, aimed at occupational inclusion in the agricultural sector of our country.

Cultum Change is the training program aimed at the social inclusion and work placement of refugees in agriculture, started by Reale Foundation, together with Confagricoltura and an Onlus Senior Age of Wisdom, with ENAPRA, FAI-Italian Beekeepers Federation, Social Farm Network, the University of Rome Tor Vergata, in collaboration with UNHCR.

Which ambitions and objectives: With this in mind, the project aims to respond to the shortage of specialized agricultural labor by creating a platform that allows refugees to have access, on the one hand, to a quality job placement and, on the other, to training courses. e-learning and job coaching.

It is therefore an innovative platform, capable of integrating job intermediation functions with distance learning functions.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Farms and small Italian producers who need skilled labor in a very short time. The companies will be selected by Confagricoltura according not only to production criteria, but also to sustainability and particular attention to working conditions.

What external input and output: refugees and holders of international protection, as individuals who are particularly disadvantaged and fragile with respect to access to the world of work

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Italy	Farms	Supply and demand match	Skilled labor	Training courses	Skilled workers for farms	2020 – on going
Farms	Italian Govern	After Covid 19 block of immigration		E-Learning	Work for refugees and holder of international protection	
Workers need	Confagricoltura			Job coaching		

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters' / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Knowledge of Confagricoltura on farms in Italy	Possibility to create online courses of ENAPRA			
Knowledge of UNHCR on refugees legislations				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

In the absence of a workforce and the impossibility of unblocking the regular immigration system, a workforce already present in the territory but without the necessary skills is used. Thus also creating the opportunity to gain experience and remain in the area in the future.

Main sources: <https://realefoundation.org/it/progetti/i-nostri-progetti/cultum-change-inclusivita-e-innovazione-715.html>

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Case 39: Radix, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

One or two key features:

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Progetto Radix /Italy

Offer sustainable alternatives to undeclared work

Running 2021 - on going

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Lazio Region presented the bill n.107 / 19 on the fight against illegal work in agriculture, completing the Protocol "For quality work ...", signed on 8 January with the involvement of the rural areas of province of Latina. Despite the widespread commitment of political bodies, trade unions and companies, which preceded the regulatory intervention, the region remains a reference point for the labor exploitation of migrants.

Which ambitions and objectives: The goal is to promote processes of co-responsibility and empowerment, within which each actor is considered as a resource and feels involved in the process of change towards communities that share the same values of legality, inclusiveness and generativity.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The project partners representing the social area, agricultural work and the local system, share the intention of seeking integrated operational solutions and the aim of offering sustainable and concrete alternatives to irregular work, to combine respect for civil rights and of dignity at work with the need of companies to face the competitiveness of the market and the search for innovative professionals.

What external input and output: The expansion of the partnership to the private social sector and to the various geographical areas that have connections with the Agro Pontino, and the systemic integration between social engagement and active inclusion define the scenario for coordination with the FAMI "Capacity Building" project, funded by Ministry of the Interior led by the CNOAS.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Lazio Region	Confagricoltura	Better employment	Picking	Inclusion guide lines	Integrations in local communities	2021- on going
Fair work rules	Lazio Governor	Better communication about migrants employment	Improved competences of workers	Easier bureaucracy for migrant workers	Co-participation of the emprise to empowerment of workers	
Migrants unemployed	Social cooperatives				Network of fair employers	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Knowledge about reality of agricultural enterprises	Complementary actions to get the results	Social cooperatives can use the knowledge of Confagricoltura	More inclusion, less racism.	
Legislative power		The Region can help the cooperatives to hire	Better economic situation, better social behaviour	
Ability to hire		Inclusion create a better social behaviour		

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

A legal and safe work create more sustainable behaviour for all the partner: some clean profit for the cooperatives, legal and ruled partner for Confagricoltura, a more inclusive society for the Lazio Region.

Main sources: <https://www.radix-tai.it/>
<https://www.confagricoltura.it/ita/area-stampa/notizie-brevi/confagricoltura-partecipa-a-radix-progetto-per-l-agricoltura-sociale-e-il-contrasto-al-caporalato>

Case 40: Food For Life, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: «Food for Life» -Spain Technological Platform / Spain (PTF4LS) Working Groups
 One or two key features: Technological Platform
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: Since 2005 and parallel to the constitution of the ETP “Food for Life”, steps were taken to constitute the Spanish Technological Platform PTF4LS. Specifically, the Spanish Food and Drinks Federation (FIAB) together with the most important agrifood research centres and being supported by the Spanish Administration founded it. More than 700 Spanish entities (SMEs, Research Centres, Universities, Cooperatives and all members of the Agrifood chain value) have been presented at the many meetings of the PTF4LS Working Groups, or at one of the conferences, workshops, projects and so on in recent years.

Which ambitions and objectives: The general objective of PTF4LS is to promote the transmission of research, scientific and technological advances through public-private collaboration of the main agri-food sector agents in relation with R+D+i, ensuring the competitiveness and growth of the agri-food sector in Spain. All this, in a prosaic way, will be carried out in agri-food R&D projects.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: The first structure of PTF4LS was absolutely based on the ETP Food for Life but over the years its structure was evolved into a more national, pragmatic one. Now there are 11 Working Groups based on different technologies and/or fields of knowledge even sectorial ones. The governance model currently counts on the Board (7 members) and the Advisory Council (8 members) that surveillance for the right development of the meetings and the activity of the PTF4LS. In addition, there is a General Assembly (155 partners) that every year approves the activity of the General Secretary who holds the daily activity of PTF4LS.

What external input and output: All the technical, knowledge provided by the partners of PTF4LS is shared with the rest of members (partners and others) trying to carry out projects that ultimately will result into different products/new processes in the Agrifood Sector.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions Rules & Incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)	
New products	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	12-36 months
New processes	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (individual/consortia)	Public/private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	12-36 months
Better products	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (consortia)	Market	Competitors, prices	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	6-24 months
Better processes	SMEs, corporations, RD centres, universities	Food and drink products	Projects (consortia)	Market	Competitors, prices	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	6-24 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + corporations. Products, processes, market	High flexibility Willingness to be applied to their products/processes	They usually become partners in RD/sustainability projects	They usually try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/Universities Basic Research	Low flexibility They are based on scientific evidences	They usually become partners in RD/sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes) goals	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Technological Centres Applied research	Medium flexibility Intermediate scale to test different technologies	They usually become partners in RD/sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/tradeoffs),):
 Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the public (and even) private funding are well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, they will comply with the rules and goals even if they are not the partner that is developing a project or a task because the whole project is considered as a single result.

Case 41: Vitartis, Spain

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: VITARTIS (Food Industry Association from *Castilla y León*) – Living Lab / Spain
 One or two key features: Regional Cluster
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

Description

History of co-creation between actors: founded in 2009, VITARTIS acts as a representative and voice of agrifood sector of the Castilla y León region. This association is formed by 65% of PYMES and 35% other big companies and institutions. But not only is formed by agrifood companies, it also integrates Technological Centers, so they can create a synergy by transferring knowledge, new methods and technological innovations.

Which ambitions and objectives: Their mission is to work for sustainability, economic and social development of the food industry from Castilla y León. Their aim is to do so by promoting innovation and representing the sector in front of public and private organizations. All this, generates an increase in competitiveness that provokes a big interest of companies and organizations in one of the most associations representing the sector, VITARTIS.

Evolution of their governance model and organization: Food Industry Association from *Castilla y León* is a private entity that works for the region, watching over the general interests, coming positions with the primary sector and the administration. Inside, we can find the **Board of Directors** (management body that ensures compliance with the purposes of the Association), **Presidents Council** (consultative body made up of all the presidents of VITARTIS since its creation) and the rest of the **Team** (composed by director, responsible of quality and innovation, administration and digital communication, responsible of technological vigilance).

What external input and output: VITARTIS conforms a link between the business world, the scientific world and research. They collect more than 130 partners, 106 approx. Are agrifood companies, the rest of them are Universities and Research centers. In this matter, VITARTIS makes up the 40% of the turnover and employment of the agrifood industry of Castilla y León. They also have since 2019 a narrow contact with DIHBU (Digital Innovation Hub Industry 4.0) and they follow the living lab strategy since then, with working groups, seminars, round tables and other interactive sessions.

Pic 1. Current governance model and organization

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a *GAME*):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (Rules & Incentives)		Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
New products	Universities, Research Centers	Enhance products from Castilla y León	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable products and positive effects in health	12-36 months
New processes and techniques	Technological Centers and Research centers	More sustainability, innovative and efficiency products	Projects together with companies	Private funding	Laws, norms, competitors	More sustainable processes (energy, waste treatments)	12-36 months
Posicioning/ representation/ Implementation of innovation plans	Partners, Companies, Federations, Associations	Promotion activities, financing, Interactive sessions know-how	Support of created projects	Private funding	Competitors and prices	More sustainable products (sources, Packaging, etc)	12-18 months
Administration and regulation	Regulatory Council, Organisations, Federations, Administration	Quality assurance, law regulations	Accreditation of projects and quality assurance	Private funding	Competitors and local regulations	More sustainable processes (energy, footprints)	12-36 months

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network, ..?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SMEs + Corporations Products, processes, market	Low flexibility Stablish plans and project	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to get a balance between technology and market goals	Yes. With companies that belong to the same business group
Research Centres/ Universities/ Associations Basic Research and Dissemination	Medium flexibility They are based on scientific evidences, they generate scientific knowledge	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They try to be more focussed on technology (applied to both product and processes) and dissemination of those	Yes. With other Research Centres/Universities involved in the technologies they are interested in
Technological centers Applied research	Medium flexibility Competitive improvement of companies and their contribution to economic development	They usually become partners in RD/ sustainability projects	They usually try to be more focussed on technology (mainly applied to processes) goals but they slightly depend on market behaviour	Yes. With other Tech Centres and/or companies involved in the technologies they are interested in. They search for new ideas in research centers

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

Every kind of actors are extremely concerned about sustainability, regarding both technologies and/or new consumer preferences. In addition, the private funding is well aligned with the sustainability transition becoming a *must* when anyone is considering to carry out any kind of project. Finally, they will comply with the rules and goals even if they are not the partner that is developing a project or a task because the whole project is considered as a single result.

Case 42: CEET, Agro-logistics, a new transport system for perishables, The Netherlands

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country CEET, the closed system for transport of 'perishables, The Netherlands **One or two key features:** 60% energy reduction; fruit and vegetable losses enormously reduced during transport and storage **Status** (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): new CEET air conditioning system implemented in maritime transport containers

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: A consortium of research institute, agro-logistics supplier, solar energy company, air-conditioning firm, auction, and energy consultancy, with support of the Dutch government started the development of a new transport container concept in 1998; now widely implemented.

Which ambitions and objectives: stand-alone storage and transport container, using solar energy for dynamically optimizing climate-storage conditions to reduce losses. **Evolution of their governance model and organisation:** From Economy-Ecology- Technology Consortium to embedded activity in its key players, still working together. **What external input and output:** Subvention from the Dutch Government of 7 million DFL and 7 million DFL own contributions for 6 years; with subsequent funding.

An illustration (Product, service, organisation change, ...)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Global transport	Auctions,	Fruit, vegetables	Washing, packaging	No chemicals for storage	Subventions	> 50% energy reduction
Localized storage (in the field or auctions)	Logistic suppliers	Flowers and flower bulbs	Storage conditioning (incl. air conditions and green chemicals)	No chemical insecticides	Legal liability for losses	No chemicals used during storage
	Energy providers	Convenience fresh products	Transport and distribution		IPR position	Losses substantially reduced (near zero)
	R&D service					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Each actor recognized expert in own area	New dynamic air conditioning systems	Cross-sector alliance	Green transport	None
All competences involved in agro-logistics	Willingness to invest in challenging trajectory	Energy – storage – fresh produce cluster	Zero loss	
			Minimal energy use	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The storage and transport sector have always been focused on static storage conditions that are most easily controlled (fixed temperatures and oxygen conditions). However, perishables like fruit are living entities, hence, optimized storage should be using dynamic control systems (DCS) steered by the minimal required oxygen needed for respiration: i.e. near coma conditions to extend shelf life as long as possible and reduce disorders / losses. The newly setup consortium, with a new DCS concept, was willing to invest money because they jointly believed in substantially reducing energy usage for storage and product losses. They succeeded after more than 10 years research and development.

Main sources: CEET project description and <https://edepot.wur.nl/263489>

Case 43: Greek National Technology Platform, Greece

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: **HELLENIC TECHNOLOGY PLATFORM / Greece**

One or two key features: **Greek National Technology Platform**

Source: <https://www.sevt.gr/en/food-for-life/HMOK/hellenic-technology-platform>

Status: **Running initiative (2009-Present)**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: In 2009, the Hellenic Technology Platform "Food for Life" was established under the management of the Federation of Hellenic Food Industries (SEVT), which represents the interests of food and drink industries at national and European level. Since its establishment, the HTP "Food for Life" has brought together the main stakeholders of the food sector namely; food and related industries, academia and research community with the aim of working together to define the Hellenic research priorities in the food chain.

Which ambitions and objectives: The vision of the Hellenic Technology Platform "Food for Life" is to achieve an effective integration of strategically-focused, national, concerted research in the field of food and nutrition science as well as consumer sciences and food chain management, that will deliver innovative and improved food products and processes for, and to, national, regional and global markets in line with consumer needs and expectations.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The European Technology Platform 'Food for Life' was created in 2005 under the auspices of the Confederation of Food and Drink Industries of the European Union (CIAA, now FoodDrinkEurope), following the principles of the Lisbon Strategy.

What external input and output: Targets: Provide vision for national renaissance; Provide an effective and sustained interaction among all stakeholders, promote increased R&D expenditure among its members; Identify research needs and priorities in the areas of nutrition, foods, aquaculture and agro-biotechnology; Coordinate food research and avoid duplication and contribute to the evaluation of research framework programs; Increase multidisciplinary/cross-sector education and researchers mobility; Ensure research funds are allocated to applied research with significant financial impact; Ensure increased confidence in the food supply chain among Greek consumers.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Greece (National)	Food industry	Strategic Research and Innovation agenda	Network	National (Greece)	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2009-Present
Innovation	Ministries	Network	Cooperation initiatives	Language (Greek)	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and env).	Project setting of actions
Food Industry including SMEs	Universities and research centres	Projects	Innovation Resources		Employment / Innovation in the region	
		Funding information	Competitiveness	Membership based		

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Platform of ministry, knowledge suppliers and industry	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for Flanders	NFTPs platform, FoodDrinkEurope platform, International outreach
Innovation	Resource facilitation		Projects at national and EU level	
Implementation				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

.....

Main sources: **SEVT (Hellenic Food Industry Federation)**

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Case 44: Cluster Agrifood Nazionale CLAN, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Cluster Agrifood Nazionale C.L.A.N / Italy

One or two key features: Italian National Agri-food Cluster

Source: <https://clusteragrifood.it/en/>

Status: Running initiative (2019-Present)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Cluster Agrifood Nazionale (CLAN) is a multi-stakeholder association in the agri-food sector that brings together companies, trade associations, universities, research organisations, training bodies and local representatives operating in the agri-food sector. It has 113 members.

Which ambitions and objectives: To promote sustainable economic growth in the Italian agri-food sector, based on research and innovation, and to increase the competitiveness and potential of SMEs, including on an international level. To foster dialogue between research, local areas and businesses in order to generate synergies and enhance the excellence of Italian-made food products through the development of a consolidated and inclusive network.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The association is administered by the Board of Directors, which acts as a steering and management body with the broadest powers of ordinary and extraordinary management. It is made up of seven board members elected by the assembly, as representatives of the three categories comprising the cluster: three from the "Business" category, two from the "Research" category and two from the "Territories" category.

What external input and output: Strategic support for policymakers; Internationalisation; Events and networking; Communication and promotion; Support for research, innovation and the technology transfer processes; Support for human capital training; Development of knowledge management systems.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Italy (National)	Food industry and agriculture	Strategic Research and Innovation agenda	Network	National (Italy)	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2019-Present
Innovation	Ministries	Network	Cooperation initiatives	Language (Italian)	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and env).	Project setting of actions
Food Industry including SMEs	Universities and research centres	Projects	Innovation Resources		Employment / Innovation in the region	
		Funding information	Competitiveness	Membership based		

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Platform of ministry, knowledge suppliers and industry	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for Italy	NFTPs platform, Italian clusters, EU outreach
Innovation	Resource facilitation		Projects at national and EU level	
Implementation				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Main sources: C.L.A.N

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Case 45: Wagralim, Belgium

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: **WAGRALIM / Belgium**

One or two key features: **Innovation platform (cluster) for the Wallonian food industry**

Source: <https://www.wagralim.be/>

Status: **Running initiative (2006-Present)**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Founded in 2006 as a non-profit organization, Wagralim is one of 6 competitiveness clusters aimed at supporting economic activity and employment in strategic areas for Wallonia. It relies mainly on collaboration between manufacturers, universities, research centers and training centres. It has more than 300 members.

Which ambitions and objectives: Wagralim is the Walloon benchmark for agri-food innovation in all its forms: process, products and market approaches. Thanks to its transversal approach, combined with a dense network of entrepreneurial and academic partners in Belgium and abroad, it catalyzes innovation within a strong ecosystem.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The organisation is lead by a board of 3 directors. The Board of Directors is supported by three observers from the Walloon Region, Departments of Economic Affairs and Employment, Research and AWEX [Walloon Export and Foreign Investment Agency]. The governance structure has 10 industrial representatives, 6 scientific members and 1 from the National Federation. The services are supported by 16 members of the secretariat.

What external input and output: The strategy is based in a sustainable and circular agri-food system: 3 strategic axes: 1. Interconnected and sustainable agri-food system, 2. Efficient and transparent industry, 3. Nutrition and Consumer. It provides a set of services: Projects R&D and training, investment projects, technological support, marketing, internationalisation, digitalisation and sustainability.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Wallonia (regional)	Food industry	Technological support	Network	Regional (Wallonia)	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2006-Present
Innovation	Regional ministry	Network	Cooperation initiatives	Language (French)	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and env).	Project setting of actions
Industry including SMEs	Universities and research centres	Marketing support	Innovation Resources	Financial sustainability from membership	Employment / Innovation in the region	
Knowledge services	Regional government (Flanders)	Projects / Funding	Competitiveness			

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Adaptation to project needs	Cluster of ministry, knowledge suppliers and industry	Strategy on a circular and sustainable food system	NFTPs platform, FoodDrinkEurope platform, International outreach
Innovation	Resource facilitation			
Implementation				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

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Main sources: **Wagralim**

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Case 46: BIM Fishery Improvement Projects, Ireland

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country : BIM Fishery Improvement Projects (FIP) / Ireland

One or two key features: Strategic platform to help fisheries become more sustainable

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Fishery Improvement Projects is a multi-stakeholders program created in 2007. The traceability aspect is led by the non profit organization FishChoice that created FisheryProgress.org, a science-based platform gathering resources to track progress and provide tools to the FIP stakeholders in order to help them implementing projects. There exist many FIPs (107) led by NGOs or industry all over the world. In Europe, the Ireland's Seafood Development Agency (BIM) is supporting 4 pilots FIPs co-partnered with the industry and working closely with Sustainable Fisheries Partnership.

Which ambitions and objectives: FIP provide a platform for fishermen, seafood buyers and suppliers to develop a strategy to improve a specific fishery by considering better policies and management over a given time period. BIM is specifically working on increasing traceability and visibility of the provenance of Irish seafood caught and process.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: If FIPs is implemented by the fishery value chain, BIM is providing them a certification (Responsibly Sourced Seafood Standard) that ensures the sustainability of the FIP sourced seafood. The partnership also includes The Irish Food Board. Together they act as platform to demonstrate the sustainability credentials of Irish fisheries.

What external input and output: Certification that could be valorised by the post-fishing value chain, scientific knowledge delivered by the advisory board, seafood projects based around the value chain associated with a specific specie (like brown crab...).

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Ireland	BIM (Ireland's Seafood Development Agency)	Responsibly Sourced Seafood Standard	Third party certification	Rules: Certification rules and FIP	Policy and fishing practices evolution	In 2021, BIM as launched a Sustainability Improver Programme
Policies and management	Fishing industries, MSC	Digital technologies (such as blockchain) to increase traceability and visibility of Irish seafood	Identifying potential new FIPs	Incentive : access the market of sustainable food products	Give fishermen a better recognition of their work effort	
	Research centres, conservation and business organisation, authorities		Developing new tools for evidence based sourcing policies		Financial sustainability : competitiveness	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Knowledge about seafood value chain and actors	Complementary actions to get the results	BIM help the value chain to get certificates and link them with international organizations	Demonstrating Ireland's commitment of achieving and maintaining sustainable fisheries	Achieving and maintaining sustainable fisheries
Scientific based solution				
International multi-actors network				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Sustainability of seafood products is the main objective. This sustainability vision is economically and politically driven to propel Ireland in the sustainable seafood products market. It seems to have less participation of fishermen.

Main sources: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31574120/>
<https://bim.ie/fisheries/sustainability-and-certification/fishery-improvement-projects/>

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Case 47: Innovation Marketing Program, Finland

Name of the food systems co-creation case : Innovation Marketing Program/ Finland

One or two key features: Marketing innovations program for sustainable fisheries products

Status: Finished (2016-2020)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Innovation program was launched in 2016 and partly financed by the EMFAF funds. This program was coordinated and driven by Pro Kala Ry, a civil NGO promoting public knowledge on fish and fisheries. Re-create a trustful link between fish industry and population. In this context, a partnership has been built with industrial fishery sectors but also chefs and NGOs.

Which ambitions and objectives: The final objective is to sustainably improve market position and sustainable fish products added-value. In that extent, it aims at developing value chain cooperation and enhance international competitiveness.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The program was piloted by a professional association and inter-professionals from industrial and local fisheries and aquaculture, as well as two chefs. This pilot board was in charge to conduct partners' network (businesses/entrepreneurs from fisheries, natural resources centre, Finnish food organizations, regional and national NGOs).

What external input and output: campaigns promoting fisheries and industry's image and sustainable fish products, events gathering actors, new technical guidelines for product promotion in the value chain, export and internationalisation of the program.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Finland	Fishing artisanal and industrial organisations	Various campaigns promoting sustainable fisheries and industry targeting Finnish population	Cooperation	Rules: EMFAF program, national and market laws	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2016-2020
Marketing and innovation	NGOs	Guidelines on quality practices all along the value chain	Promoting	Incentives: open to international exchanges	More jobs in fisheries sectors and a better image of the sector	
Fish products value chain	Chefs	Consumer research	Innovation		Sustainable fish products added-value	
Connection industrial – population		National Fish Soup Day implemented in Finland				

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Original approach by connecting industry and population	Adaptation to fisheries professionals needs	Program partnership	Improve fish products added value and market place	exportation and internationalisation of the program (training session, exchanges on industries concerns, Finland pavillon at Seafood Expo Brussels...)
The entire value chain is present with specific knowledge	Formation, knowledge transfer		More cooperation between actors of the value chain	
			Improve industrial and fishery sector public image	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

A mix between industrial concerns and sustainability. Each aspect of the sustainability is covered (environmental, social, financial).

Main sources: <https://merikalatalous.fi/innovaatio-ohjelmat/markkinoinnin-innovaatio-ohjelma/>
<https://prokala-fi.translate.google.com/markkinointiohjelma-mahdollistaa-viestija-rakentaa-verkostoja/>

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Case 48: Naturskansom, Denmark

Name of the food systems co-creation case / CountryNaturSkansom – Denmark

One or two key features:collective brand, national development strategy

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors : This brand has been released in 2020 within a partnership composed by experts, firms and the Danish ministry for food, agriculture and fishery. It is the first labelling scheme in the world for a sustainable fishery to be controlled by the public authorities. This national brand was proposed for the first time by the National Association for a Cleaner Sea (Levende Hav Landforeningen) in 1995 before it became a concrete political decision in 2016.

Which ambitions and objectives : offer fish products respecting biodiversity by healthy populations, enhancing coastal fishery and availability in various places (from groceries to school canteens). There are 5 main rules focused on both fisheries practices and fishes populations control.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: from a maritime professionals association idea to the creation of a partnership advised by a panel of experts.

What external input and output: a new market opportunities for coastal fishermen and the entire value chain, more knowledge about fishing gears' impact on the biodiversity, innovation at the international scale (first country to develop national labelling scheme for sustainable fishery)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
National scale	Public authorities, NGOs, research institute	National recognition of oceans issues and international vitrine of best practices	Labelling food products	Quality requirements for each product chains	More sustainable fishery practices	Idea launched in 1995 before being implemented in 2020
Local fisheries, processing, sales level	Fishermen organizations, food industry, retailers	Labelled seafood products	Fishing practises, processing, retailing, consumption	Fulfilment of quality, fishing gears and practices requirements	Marine professional s motivation	Added value for local costal fishermen and the rest of value chain dealing with these products (social and economic aspects)

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Professionals and experts knowledges (complementary)	Everybody can suggest improvements (consumer, fishermen...), not only experts	Advisory board on the brand development	Marine biodiversity and environment preservation	A common brand 'NaturSkansom'
Willingness of all the value chain actors together with Government	Fishermen have to adapt their practices if they want to get involved	Partnership between ministry and organisations/industries...	Giving more choice to the consumers	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

.... Real pride of the actors of the partnership to be involved in this national engagement.

Main sources: <https://xn--naturskansom-38a.dk/>
<https://skaansomtystfiskeri.dk/naturskaansom-2/>

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Case 49: Pôle Mer Méditerranée, France

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country **Pôle Mer Méditerranée/France**

One or two key features: **Innovation platform**

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): **running**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Launched in 2000 by the Marine & Submarine Network to stimulate collaboration between smalls and big firms, research actors around one precise theme. Pole Mer Méditerranée also interacts with his brother site Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique in order to exchange their skills and experiences.

Which ambitions and objectives: The main objective is to sustainably develop blue economy, including fisheries, through innovation. It is first created to stimulate competitiveness but sustainability is on top of the agenda.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Implemented together with research centres (such as Ifremer, Marseille Oceanology Centre) and regional firms. Public actors have been integrated in the partnership after having been labelled "Pôle de compétitivité".

What external input and output: call for regional sustainable projects via public funds, services for supporting firms growth.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)	
Région Sud	Small firms, groups	Regional economic development projects	Calling for projects	Market laws, language (French)	Support Research and development projects	Financing sustainability-oriented projects	2000 : creation of Toulon Var Technologies
Blue Economy	Research centre	Services for enhancing businesses' growth	Supporting regional blue economy business			Supporting the development of small regional business	2005 : labelled "pôle de compétitivité"
	Ecosystem (professional associations, banks, consultants...)					Financial sustainability of the region via innovation and competitiveness	2013 : Pôle PACA become Pôle Méditerranée because of its new international ambitions

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Pôle Mer Med is very close to blue economy actors and is present in many regional projects	Complementary actions to get the results	Kind of cluster that is driven by the Pole Med team	Enhance sustainable blue economy of the French Med regions	Enhance sustainable blue economy around the Mediterranean and at the international scale
Key actors in marine innovation gathered		Pole Med organize a lot of workshops where the actors can meet and exchange		

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

They are present in some key sustainability regional projects, even if there are no direct economic benefits for the actors included. Pole Med have globally a technological vision of the sustainability. They want to be a vitrine of sustainable blue economy at the international levels and get included in various Interreg Med.

Case 50: NCE Seafood Innovation, Norway

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: **NCE Seafood Innovation / Norway**

One or two key features: **Seafood industry cluster**

Status: **Running initiative (2015-Present)**

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The cluster consists of 70 partners, representing a total of 150 small and medium-sized businesses. The cluster plays a leading role in the sustainable development of the industry through significant investments in research, development and innovation. It is also known as the Norwegian Centres of Expertise Seafood Innovation.

Which ambitions and objectives: NCE Seafood Innovation aims to contribute to sustainable seafood growth, by focusing on innovation and facilitating interactions across the industry.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The board is composed of different industry representatives. Four times a year, the cluster gather experts and business leader for discussions around cluster's strategy organized in focus groups : Climate, environment and circular economy, Digital transformation and digitalization, Fish health and welfare, Future feed ingredients and Future competence and talent attraction.

What external input and output: knowledge by research institutes, projects, industry insights, talent recruitment, incubator implementation, EU funding advices

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Norway	Aquaculture industries, SME and start-ups	Projects and programs	Networking	Rules: national laws, market rules, fees membership	Competitiveness (financial sustainability)	2015-Present
Innovation and research	Universities and research centres	Meeting arenas	Advising professional actors	Incentives: open to international, multi-scales businesses	Projects in sustainable initiatives (social and environment)	102 members in 2021
Seafood sector	Investment companies	Future Ocean Incubator	Project management and financing		Employment	
		Industry insight reports				

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Network (including SMEs)	Relevant advice regarding professionals needs	Industrial cluster	Fulfil the UN's sustainability goals	"world leading cluster" in aquaculture sector
Research and innovation	Funding		Further growth within the seafood industry	
Represent the entire seafood value chain			Promoting team efforts	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Sustainability on top of the agenda together with growth economy. Focus on tech and digitalization.

Main sources: <https://seafoodinnovation.no/>
<https://www.strategytools.io/nce-seafood-innovation-cluster-success-story/>

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Case 51: Sustainable Food Procurement, Denmark

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: 90% organic public procurement in Copenhagen motor for organic private sales and organic farmland

One or two key features: Public Procurement

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running since 2001

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: since 2001 the Municipality of Copenhagen works towards 90% organic public procurement collaboration closely with the House of Food (an independent, non – commercial foundation) causing a scaling effect on organic land till and organic product use in private contexts (restaurants, hotels etc.)

Which ambitions and objectives: primary objective was 100% organic public procurement in the municipality of Copenhagen

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: ?

What external input and output: High external output on organic production infrastructure and availability of organic products in Denmark

Source: Holmbeck 2020 Shows: Increase in organic cuisine Labels for private sector since 2011

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Public procurement	Municipality / local government	Calls, laws, budget	Legal fram, setting incentives for organic procurement, auditing	Federal legislation on procurement, staff availability for auditing, conceptualization of procurement criteria	best practice example on procurement of organic product, increased staff knowledge on procurement changes, highly increased infrastructure, land use and supply for organic products	2014 - now
Public catering	80 large public kitchens	Organic Ingredients	Planning meal schedules, organizing & training chefs, delivering to public institutions	market supply margins, Procurement, specification, Audits, staff knowledge on cooking	90% organic meals little price increase due to less meat, less exposition to pesticide residues for consumers increased intake of freshly processed foods	2014 - now
Production & Processing	Suppliers (farmers, processing)	organic products, raw products, processed products	Growing and processing organic food, acquire certificates accordingly	certification rules according to certification agency, procurement, margins	Increase in organic production of 70% since 2011, Increase in local Biodiversity, soil improvement, intercroops, less groundwater pollution, decrease in Co2 emissions due to short and efficient transport	2014 - now
Private sector	Restaurants, hotels, caterings, canteens	meals	Interface with end-consumer; marketing through ecological labels, menu adapting prices or reducing meat-use	Demand for organic pricy meals, purchasing power of the consumer offer/supply of fresh organic foods	higher percentage of organic meals (depending on label 30, 60 or 90%) less exposition to pesticide residues for consumers	Since 2011 an increased use of organic labels

Main sources: Holmbeck 2020: Best practice in organic public procurement; https://www.organicseurope.bio/content/uploads/2021/06/FOAMOE_Best-Practice-in-Organic-Public-Procurement_The-case-of-Denmark.pdf?dd https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/news_alert/Issue47_Case_Study97_Copenhagen.pdf

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Municipality: law insights, strong influence on procurement criteria, purchasing power	Very high: cooperation with House of Food & "Organic Denmark" from the beginning of the transition towards increase of organic foods	Municipality with House of Food (as knowledge Hub), Organic Denmark (organic sectors association)	All involved organizations saw the potential of organic public procurement	Not proven: Joint objective with organic farmers to increase organic sales (?)
Farmers: production skills, knowledge of certification	High: Adapting strongly to demand of public and private procurement, adapting to certification rules	Little: mostly through procurement demands, intermediate interaction with catering services/restaurants	Individual, but maybe: Goal to provide healthy, little processed and environmental friendly foods	Not proven: Objective to increase sale of products
Catering: skills in food preparation (individual), conceptualizing skills meal plan	High: Adapting to procurement criteria, consumer needs and wishes, vegetable supply/changes (due to weather, season etc.)	Little: intermediate interaction with farmers/supplier of food	Individual, but maybe: Goal to provide healthy, little processed and environmental friendly foods	unknown
Private sector: powerful marketing, strong role model function, purchasing power	High: Very adaptive to consumer demand, adaptive to food supply	unknown	Increase in consumer willingness to pay for and consume organic food (common focus with municipality)	unknown

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Especially the municipality of Copenhagen shows an understanding of its own responsibility:

- in changing supply infrastructure for organic products
- in building up long lasting partnerships for structural change
- in seeing their purchasing power and changing it to sustainable purchasing habits
- in setting an example and procuring the most environmental friendly foods
- in actual influence on groundwater quality, biodiversity, soil degradation, CO₂ – Emissions through production of herb - & pesticide, CO₂- Emission through fossil fuel use in transportation, health of Vienna's population, intact local ecosystems (having a positive impact on human health)

The strong success of the Danish model can be tracked back to financing of education in kitchens while raising the percentage of ecological ingredients. Chefs were able to adapt new menus that lowered the use of meat, so price increases could be held at a reasonable level. Also the very clear and well defined criteria were crucial for success.

The farmers producing the organic vegetables show a high willingness to apply sustainable behaviour because they had (in the past) or due to the new procurement criteria will convert their processes in order to fit the criteria of Austrian/European Ecological Criteria. This process is very difficult due to the financial and cognitive resources required. Therefore it is a long-term decision the farmers make, where they show high trust and willingness to contribute to a sustainability transition.

The catering services had to apply for the call (administrative term for application process to contract subcontractors) the municipality of Copenhagen published. Seven bidders applied, two of which were able to comply with sustainability award criteria. The two bidders were therefore proven to individually work on the topic of sustainable procurement – even before the call was published.

The private sector in this case shows an extremely high willingness to adapt to the systemic change. When supply of organic products started to rise the implementation of organic labels in the private sector did accordingly.

Main sources: Holmbeck 2020: Best practice in organic public procurement; https://www.organicseurope.bio/content/uploads/2021/06/IFOAMOE_Best-Practice-in-Organic-Public-Procurement_The-case-of-Denmark.pdf?d
https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/news_alert/Issue47_Case_Study97_Copenhagen.pdf

Case 52: Sustainable Food Procurement, Austria

Name of the food systems co-creation case/ Country: Procuring healthy and sustainable vegetables for Vienna's nursing homes

One or two key features: Public Procurement

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running since 2020

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: ?

Which ambitions and objectives: organic procurement of “earthy vegetables” in Vienna's public nursing homes (vegetables growing close to the earth)

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: ?

What external input and output: ?

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Catering	Nursing home kitchen/canteen	Organic Ingredients/ earthy vegetables for daily meals	planning meal schedules, organizing chefs & training, catering, interface to consumer	market supply, margins, procurement specification, availability of in-house, kitchen audits, staff knowledge on processing foods	100% organic earthy vegetables, less exposition to pesticide residues, increased intake of freshly processed vegetables	2020 - 2022
Public procurement	Municipality /local government	Calls, laws, budgeting	legal frame setting incentives for organic procurement	Federal legislation on procurement, staff availability for auditing/conceptualization of procurement criteria	Best practice example on procurement of organic products, increased staff knowledge on procurement changes	2020 - 2022
Production	Suppliers (farmers, processing)	Organic “earthy vegetables”	growing “earthy vegetables” Acquire according certificates	certification rules according to certification agency, Procurement, margins	increase in organic production: Increase in local Biodiversity, soil improvement, intercrops less groundwater, pollution, decrease in Co2 emissions due to short and efficient transport	2020 - 2022

Main sources:

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/news_alert/Issue_99_Case_Study_187_Vienna.pdf
<https://www.digital.wienbibliothek.at/wbrup/download/pdf/3559563?originalFilename=true>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPaths; WP 4

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Funded by the European Union

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Municipality: law insights, strong influence on procurement criteria, purchasing power	Low: only adapting to federal legislation on procurement	unknown	No, it's a rather hierarchical process were municipality plans to change procurement structure and local supply chains	Not proven: Joint objective with organic farmers to increase organic sales subsequently to increasing organic land use (?)
Farmers: production skills, knowledge of certification	High: Adapting strongly to demand of public procurement, adapting to certification rules	Little: mostly through procurement demands, intermediate interaction with catering services	Individual, but maybe: Goal to provide healthy, little processed and environmental friendly foods	Not proven: Objective to increase sale of products
Catering: skills in food preparation (individual), conceptualizing skills meal plan	High: Adapting to procurement criteria, consumer needs and wishes, vegetable supply/changes (due to weather, season etc.)	Little: intermediate interaction with farmers/supplier of food	Individual, but maybe: Goal to provide healthy, little processed and environmental friendly foods	unknown

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Especially the municipality of Vienna shows an understanding of its own responsibility:

- in changing supply infrastructure for organic products
- in seeing their purchasing power and changing it to sustainable purchasing habits
- in setting an example and procuring the most environmental friendly foods
- in actual influence on groundwater quality, biodiversity, soil degradation, Co2 – Emissions through production of herb - & pesticide, Co2- Emission through fossil fuel use in transportation, health of Vienna's population, intact local ecosystems (having a positive impact on human health)

The farmers producing the organic vegetables show a high willingness to apply sustainable behaviour because they had (in the past) or due to the new procurement criteria will convert their processes in order to fit the criteria of Austrian/European Ecological Criteria. This process is very difficult due to the financial and cognitive resources required. Therefore it is a long-term decisions the farmers make, where they show high trust and willingness to contribute to a sustainability transition.

The catering services had to apply for the call (administrative term for application process to contract subcontractors) the municipality of Vienna published. Four bidders applied, all of which were able to comply with sustainability award criteria. All four bidders are therefore proven to individually work on the topic of sustainable procurement – even before the call was published.

Main sources:

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/news_alert/Issue_99_Case_Study_187_Vienna.pdf
<https://www.digital.wienbibliothek.at/wbrup/download/pdf/3559563?originalFilename=true>

Annex 3: Table summarizing WP7 cases presented in annex 4

Case number	Cases's names and country	Case number	Cases brief description
1	Food Council Berlin , Germany	20	The Sustainable Food Systems Program (SPNF-PKKKY) Himachal Pradesh, India
2	Circular economy for food , International	21	Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM) , Tanzania
3	4 per 1000 , International	22	Sustainable Food Places , United Kingdom
4	ResQ Club , Finland	23	Biocode , Finland
5	A New York City Framework for Good Purchasing , United-States	24	Regional Networks for Fair Consumption (REKO) , Nordic countries
6	Shifting Urban Diets: Operationalizing Food System Targets for Health and Sustainability , Denmark	25	Vegan Challenge , Finland
7	Milano Food Policy , Italy	26	Refugees in the food system of a medium-sized city , Poland
8	Milan Pact Award , award, Italy		
9	One Planet Network , International		
10	Organic Cities Europe , Europe		
11	Climate Smart Chefs , European Union		
12	EU Food Policy Coalition , European Union		
13	The Sustainable Restaurant Association , United Kingdom		
14	Semences Paysanes , France		
15	Eating Better , United Kingdom		
16	Mit Eszel platform , Hungary		
17	Dynamics for an Agroecological Transition in Senegal (DyTAES) , Senegal		
18	Etiquetable , France		
19	Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean (SFS-MED) platform , Italy		

Annex 4: WP7 case studies

Case 1: Food Council Berlin, Germany

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Food Council Berlin/Germany

One or two key features: network of citizens to influence urban food policy

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

Which ambitions and objectives: in a local food strategy the food council Berlin developed guidelines for a local sustainable food system, along the whole value-chain, now it is in the process of realizing this strategy

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The food council Berlin is made up of different entities, the board of directors and the circle of speakers who all represent one working group with a specific food related topic

What external input and output: the food council Berlin works in different structures: allows citizens to engage, appears as entity in EU-projects and interacts closely with the local government. Therefore the external in- and output is high.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Local food system Berlin	Citizens, local politicians, local and international NGO's and research (secondary actor)	mainly local action in close cooperation with citizens, local food strategy, part of FoodCLIC (EU project)	open discussion and city dialogue on transformation of the local food system → followed by implication in projects or political lobbying activities	Dependent on external funding such as EU- or local funding, dependent on citizen engagement, dependent on "openness" from the local government towards a change in food policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a concrete food strategy paper • funding for a FoodCampus • Book Release "Berlin isst anders" • action-focused conference on the local food system 	founded in 2016; since app. 2 - 3 years a player in european food policy and project management

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • many years of experience in citizen engagement • activism coupled with scientific skills • internationally renown and included in european networks/research projects 	very high level of flexibility towards citizens and their needs in terms of local food systems → work with a democratic bottom - up approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network activities with other german food councils • included in EU-projects → therefore interaction with european partners • self-understanding of being a platform for all stakeholders of the local food system • interaction with local government 	The cluster, as in "all engaged stakeholders of local value chains", has the joint goal to transform the regional food system and value-chain towards more sustainability, equality and fairness	Tries to set up a "Network of Food Councils" for Germany, but the funding stopped; also coach other civil entities who want to build up food councils and support them

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Very action focused, both on a local as on a european level. The process they make towards sustainability is to be considered quite big, with their impact on Berlin food policies through their food strategy paper as well as their international impact through Horizon-projects. The Food Council Berlin has paid staff instead of a being reliant on volunteers which enhances their influence and efficiency. One good example is the planned food-Campus, which is a mayor project to connect citizens to learn and discuss about food and also the "LebensMittelPunkte" which are local food-distribution and gathering- spaces

Main sources: <https://ernaehrungsrat-berlin.de/>

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

It addresses global value-chains and focuses on regional food consumption. Also concentrates on food inequalities inside cities, local infrastructure problems (such as "LebensMittelPunkte"), unsustainable public procurement practices, food loss and unsustainable packaging, and so on; they really focus on every part of the value chain

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Specific projects are implemented after collecting citizens and local stakeholders views, such as a FoodCampus, local distribution and gathering points ("LebensMittelPunkte") and lobbying activities.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

They see sustainable food chains as closely linked to equality. Both can just be implemented together, eg. a sustainable value chain ist also a just, democratic and inclusive value chain without power centralization.

Main sources: <https://ernaehrungsrat-berlin.de/>

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Case 2: Circular economy for food, International

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Ellen MacArthur Foundation

One or two key features: City Self Assessment to understand specific solutions in the area of food/circular economy

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

CIRCULAR ECONOMY FOR FOOD: city government self-assessment

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The foundation brings together industry leading corporations, emerging innovators, affiliate Networks, government authorities, regions and cities in their "Network", where they have open discussion, share knowledge and experience. All dedicated to the topic of circular economy.

Which ambitions and objectives: The objective of the City Self Assessment is to help cities analyse their current state of the city food system and to subsequently find out in which areas a city could approve

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The Foundation was built up by Ellen MacArthur (fastes solo sailor to sail around the world) to enhance circular economy and is now supported by different partners such as BlackRock, Danone, Gucci, H&M, Ikea, Intesa SanPaolo, Nestle, Coca-Cola, Unilever

What external input and output:

External input of expert knowledge by partners; Largest Congress for circular Economy and networking activities inside the crucial industry as an output; other outputs are education and learning resources openly accessible on the website as well as tools and guidance for businesses

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
City Food System	Municipalities	knowledge, advise, assessment	Analysing the current Food System	Assessed cities must have knowledge and data about the city food system	very precise advise on how to make the Food system more circular	Filling out the assessment form when data are complete: 15 Minutes

Main sources: <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/city-self-assessment>

Contact person: ?

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The Foundation and the network have insights and expert knowledge on innovation, business and research in circular economy	The Foundation is in any case a very inclusive actor towards all sectors (industry, research, cities, etc.)	Yes! As explained above.	The Foundation defines a certain goal (circular economy) and gathers partners that support this goal while having other own goals (eg. sales, marketing, etc.)	The Foundation looks at all sectors through the lenses of circular economy

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The Foundations ratio is quite big since big players of the food industry are partners. Their Network is also big (100+ partners) and the conference is well-known in the circular economy "bubble". The willingness to take action comes from the founders own experience of sailing around the earth with a finite of resources, which she applies to global economy. Her goal is to make economy circular by design, not just by recycling: All products must be designed to be reused in another way after their time is up. In terms of food this means using all parts of a food (reduction of food waste) and using the food waste as fuel (reusing of food waste).

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

- Food Waste inside the production chain: Many "parts" of live stock, plants, crops are not used to feed humans, which leads to an unsustainable over-production.
- Packaging: Not all Cities have established an sufficient recycling system
- Transportation: Food is shipped from overseas, poor infrastructure for regional food commerce, regional food production is unable to produce sufficient foods

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

This case deals mainly with the topic of circular economy and food systems. Therefore, the main focus lies in creating nature-positive foods, regenerative food production and reduction or recycling of packaging. nature-positive foods means foods that use ingredients that come from regenerative agriculture or are upcycled (eg. cookies made from left-over flour from plant-based milk production, cocoa fruit pulp, crop leftovers). In regard to the City self assessment also the topic of regional sale structures for foods is an important topic.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The main focus is circularity: The Sustainable Food Systems gives back as much to nature and soil as it takes out. All waste and packaging is recycled.

Main sources: <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/city-self-assessment>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

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Case 3: 4 per 1000, International

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: 4 per 1000 initiative / International, The Executive Secretariat is hosted by The Alliance Bioversity International-CIAT, (France).

One or two key features: The International “4 per 1000” Initiative encourages stakeholders to engage in a transition towards a regenerative, productive, highly resilient agriculture, based on appropriate land and soil management, which creates jobs and income and thus leads to sustainable development.

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Farmers, economic players, local authorities and States then joined forces with researchers around the initiative, recorded on the solutions agenda (Lima-Paris Agenda for Action) during this same COP.

Which ambitions and objectives: 24 objectives under 6 goals in the strategic plan

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: 744 members and partners, 104 countries of origin, 67 producer organizations

What external input and output: CO² into the soil, output is the reduced emissions.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Soil	Agriculture, i.e. farmers	Healthy soils	Primary food production in fields	30-40 cm layer of soil in agricultural or forestry use	Reduction of carbon from the atmosphere	20-30 years
	Forestry, i.e. forest owners, governments	Food from fields				

Main sources: 4p1000.org

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; W7

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Enhancing biological processes for carbon capture to increase the levels of soil carbon	Concentrating activities in soils creates flexibility as the places for activities can be found nearly everywhere	Collaboration between stakeholders of the "Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU)"	Accelerating climate change mitigation	Vision: Worldwide healthy and carbon-rich soils to combat climate change and end hunger.
			Intensifying the adaptation of agriculture to climate change	
			Improve food security	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The activities of the initiative will significantly increase the sustainability of the food system.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Carbon emissions in the atmosphere, reduced soil health

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Improving soil health via regenerative practices in agriculture and forestry

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use? The Strategic plan includes six goals, the baseline and targets for 2030 and 2050, enabling the monitoring of the initiative

Main sources: 4p1000.org

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; W7

Case 4: ResQ Club, Finland

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country : ResQ Club / Finland

One or two key features: ...An application connecting restaurants, cafes and grocery stores to customers who want to reduce food waste in an affordable manner
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Brings food waste products to one easily accessible platform

Which ambitions and objectives: Reaching zero food waste

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Private company

What external input and output: Food waste problem, growth of the use of mobile applications

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Restaurants, cafes, grocery stores	People who work at the restaurants, cafes and grocery stores	Waste quality meals, snacks, groceries	ResQ application	Use of cellphone and a mobile app with the use of a payment method are required	Less food waste	0-4 hours from the food provider to the customer depending on the customer
	Customers			Waste food		

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Answering to the needs of food providers and customers	The service is offered to various food providers and is therefore very flexible	Actors are supported by campaigns and materials	Reduction of food waste from food providers	Working in cooperation with restaurants and other food service providers.
Connecting the support for sustainability to affordable pricing				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Functions in 124 / 309 municipalities in Finland.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Food waste

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Support for food service providers and grocery stores to use food waste

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The number of meals rescued and the reduced amounts of wasted food.

Influences SDG 12, responsible production and consumption, 13 Climate Action

Main sources: www.resq-club.com

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS, WP7

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Funded by the European Union

Case 5: A New York City Framework for Good Purchasing, United-States

Name of the food systems co-creation case / CountryA New York City Framework for Good Food Purchasing / USA

One or two key features: ...it try to answer an urgent problem that characterizes several context about the flow of communication between different realms/contexts and area.....

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Which ambitions and objectives: The program seeks to improve the food the City serves to most vulnerable populations, including school children, older adults, people in homeless shelters or held in our prisons. Implementing GFP allows the city to measure and improve performance across the different areas

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The City of New York spends nearly half a billion dollars on food each year to serve more than 230 million meals to our City's most vulnerable populations. The program has been developed to establish a transparent, clear foundation for tracking food purchases and monitoring performance annually with clear data tied to metrics: nutrition, local economies, a valued workforce, environmental sustainability, and animal welfare

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food aids	farmers	Food aids		There are several legal restrictions that this programme is trying to overcome	Monitoring framework	
monitoring	Officers, municipalities					

Main sources:<https://www.nyc.gov/site/foodpolicy/good-food-purchasing/dashboard.page>.....

Contact person:

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP7.....

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
	Different actors are put together to collect information and systematize the food system and logistics. In this sense all are forced to adapt to each other and share information adaptation	Share information	The municipality define a common aim	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision-making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

This framework, developed by The Center for Good Food Purchasing, who is partnered with The City of New York on this effort, is a values-based procurement framework that helps institutions better understand the source of the food they purchase, and provides a methodology to quantify the impact of that food along five core values: nutrition, local economies, valued workforce, environmental sustainability, and animal welfare.

As a collaborative city wide initiative managed by the Mayor's Office of Food Policy, NYC has developed its own approach to integrate the GFP principles, ensuring that money spent on food serves both the people and the planet.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

In order to save food and ameliorate the diet of people with lower means it is important to understand the availabilities, what there is in excess and what are the missing products, where are the most frequent food lost located in the system etc. This programme, which requires a collection of information requires also to align and create contact between actors that are not traditionally used to communicate. In that sense it is innovative and extremely urgent.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Frequently the lack of information represents one of the greatest problem we have. This programme is answering this problem.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

This framework is meant to develop these indicators on food purchased and food waste.

Main sources:<https://www.nyc.gov/site/foodpolicy/good-food-purchasing/dashboard.page>.....

Contact person:

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

Case 6: Shifting Urban Diets: Operationalizing Food System Targets for Health and Sustainability, Denmark

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Shifting Urban Diets: Operationalizing Food System Targets for Health and Sustainability / Copenhagen, Denmark

One or two key features: health and sustainable food system

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

Co-funded by the
European Union

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The project builds on a 2017 EIT Climate-KIC project that investigated how municipalities can develop relevant metrics and methods to identify, implement, and evaluate urban food systems interventions.

Which ambitions and objectives: The 3-year project 'Shifting Urban Diets: Operationalizing Food System Targets for Health and Sustainability' is working with the City of Copenhagen and partners to translate the findings of the EAT-Lancet Commission on Food, Planet, Health into local action and interventions

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Launched in 2019 and funded by EIT Climate-KIC, Shifting Urban Diets aims to enable cities to set smarter and more ambitious food system targets with greater accountability and measurable benefits to climate, environment, public health, and societal well-being. Shifting Urban Diets is the first initiative to operationalize the EAT-Lancet science, paving the way for a Planetary Health Diet. With Copenhagen as a prototype and other cities consulted throughout, the project will demonstrate how scientific targets for food systems can be operationalized in the city context

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diet	City of Copenhagen, EAT Lancet Commission, EIT Climate-KIC and other research partner	relevant metrics and methods to identify, implement, and evaluate urban food systems interventions	Changing in citizens habits	Support from the local Municipality	New food habits that are more sustainable and safer for the planet and society as well as smart indicators to measure implement, and evaluate urban food systems interventions	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The main strength of the Copenhagen initiative lies in the support from the Municipality as well as the cultural and social framework in which it is developed, but also the presence of valuable research institutions		The diversity of the actors in the project contribute to make it a success	Actors lay different role but all actors contribute in defining the final goals	Open interaction between partners

Main sources: https://eatforum.org/content/uploads/2022/04/EAT_Shifting-Urban-Diets_Project_Report.pdf

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

In order to be carried out this project requires a cultural and social context that recognize the relevance of the problem as well as funding and time to be developed. The municipality needs to be engaged in the first place.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The practice was developed to make the local Food system more safe and sustainable for the planet and citizens.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Actors from different background are gathered together and attention is given to indicators and new form of data analysis.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The project aims to set smarter and more ambitious food system targets with greater accountability and measurable benefits to climate, environment, public health, and societal well-being.

Main sources: https://eatforum.org/content/uploads/2022/04/EAT_Shifting-Urban-Diets_Project_Report.pdf

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Case 7: Milano Food Policy, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Food Policy / Italy

One or two key features: health and sustainable food system

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Food Policy is the city's food policy. It represents one of the legacies of Expo 2015, and is a support tool for city government promoted in synergy by the Municipality of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation to make the Milanese food system more sustainable

Which ambitions and objectives: 1. ensure healthy food for all 2. promote the sustainability of the food system 3. educate about food 4. fight against waste 5. scientific research

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: the Milan Food Policy was launched in 2015 and gradually entered the municipality governance moving from an office in the municipality to become a direction

What external input and output:

https://youtu.be/tr_vCYQh1LU?list=PLHd5UJ5aE67pcy59XCbPTFrleQmndwgxK

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diet	Milan Municipality, NGOs, Foundations, Researchers, civil society	Projects, new policies and regulations	Projects, events, community of practices, network	Support from the Milan Municipality Governance and of Cariplo Foundation as neutral actor	New projects, new local hubs, new regulations and new policies	Actions can least form few months up to many years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The main strength of the Milan Food Policy lies in long term engagement of the Milan Municipality and Cariplo Foundation	The Milan Food Policy can not be considered a flexible actor but it enjoys Cariplo Foundation's flexibility while can beneficiate from the strategic relevance of the Milan Municipality	The main strength of the Milan Food Policy lies in the ability to create connections between all actors of the Milan Urban Food System	Cariplo Foundation and Milan Municipality jointly define their goals every years	Milan Food Policy interacts with other Municipalities all over the word to share and transfer local best practices on sustainable food system

Main sources: <https://foodpolycymilano.org/en/objectives-and-priorities/>

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What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The practice was developed in order to foster the development of a more sustainable food system in the city of Milan

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The practice started with the mapping activity of the food system and the development of a government approach that included two main actors (Milan Municipality and Cariplo Foundation) and gradually starting from this it was developed a policy for the city and a network that sees the participation of many different actors from different food system areas.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

We developed a number of indicators related to the different projects that characterize the food policy. There is no single indicator. We have indicator to measure impact of dietary change in terms of CO2 production for example. Indicator on the number of actors active in the policy etc etc

Main sources: <https://foodpolicymilano.org/en/objectives-and-priorities/>

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Case 8: Milan Pact Award, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Milan Pact Award

One or two key features: foster sustainable food systems

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors One of the most important goals of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPF), is to stimulate the exchange of practices and learning between signatory cities. To foster this collaboration since 2016 the City of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation launched the Milan Pact Awards (MPA) with the aim of recognizing the most creative efforts and monitoring which cities were implementing the commitments they had made when they joined the pact. The awards are a means of encouraging action, facilitating the emergence of the best practices of the MUFPF cities, making them evident to the community with a function of inspiring the action of other signatory cities

Which ambitions and objectives: To foster the collaboration between MUFPF cities and Cariplo Foundation strength local urban food systems

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: since the beginning Cariplo Foundation and the Milan Municipality worked together on the Award

What external input and output:

<https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/award/>

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
International	Municipalities	New best practices and new food policies	Rewarding best practices	Awards (50k annually contribution + in kind engagement of local actors)	New best practices and new food policies, new signatories cities for the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact	The Award has been launched annually or every 2 years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The award represents an inspiration and a model for others grant making organization engaged on food policies . The awards represent an achievement for all municipalities active on food policies		Actors thanks to the Milan secretary interacts internationally	1. Governance 2. Sustainable diets and nutrition 3. Social and economic equity 4. food production 5. food supply and distribution 6. food waste	International collaboration across municipalities

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This activity overcome geographical differences creating a network that shares information, knowledge and best practices all around the world. During COVID pandemic this action has been extremely important as it allowed for sharing emergency answers to similar problems. In general, this action is crucial because it allow to not replicate errors fostering food system transformation all around the world in an inclusive and open way.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The practice does requires certain funding and some level of engagement and in kind contribution from the actors supporting it.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

There are more than 250 practices collected in over 6 years. I would say this is the most relevant indicator.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

For it's sustainability it requires the engagement of Cariplo Foundation and the Milan Municipality.

Main sources: <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/award/>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP7

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Funded by the European Union

Case 9: One Planet Network, International

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: One Planet Network, Sustainable Food Systems Programme

One or two key features: the network is a multi-stakeholder international initiatives that unites cities, enterprises, NGOs etc

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

Which ambitions and objectives: catalyzing urgent transformation towards sustainable food systems, as a critical strategy to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The SFS Programme (SFSP) is part of the broader One Planet Network (OPN): the network that created six sustainability programmes to implement the United Nations 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production (10YFP), which were created by the Heads of State at the Rio+20 UN Conference on Sustainable Development in 2012. The multi-actor AgriFood Task Force prepared the launch of the 10YFP on SFS, which was officially launched in 2015 as SDG target 12.1. The 10YFP was renamed as the OPN in 2017. In 2022, and following the the UN Secretary General's Food System Summit in 2021, the OPN-SFSP aims to build synergies and nurture cooperation among a wide array of actors and initiatives by supporting the implementation of the Commitments, Action Areas and Coalitions created during the UNFSS.

What external input and output: The outputs are awareness raising on food security and nutrition topics, building capacity and enable conditions for food systems to adapt sustainable practices, tools and methodologies to support governments in the transformation process and partnership building

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
the network engages on all levels due to regional as well as international partnerships and bring together "unusual allies"	everyone involved in food; with a special focus on regional government s	knowledge, best-practice, education, collaboration, experience and expertise	advocacy and conceptual as well as action-oriented work implemented by collaborative initiatives at global, regional and national/local levels	the network stays on a very theoretical meta-level	Bi-yearly conference on Sustainable Food Systems development and next steps; Tools such as E-Learning, case studies; research on Multi-Stakeholder Mechanisms as a possibility for system change → bringing together unusual allies with a whole system approach	2012-2015 : Agrifood Task Force 2017-2022 : One Planet network 2022 – ... : UNFSS follow-up

Main sources: <https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/programmes/sustainable-food-systems>

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Tackling interrelated challenges by using a system-based approach and including multiple actors	Very adaptive towards players in the food sector as well as to new challenges; including "unusual allies" is an incentive	the network fosters "multi-stakeholder mechanisms" such as food councils, sustainable food labs, which then try to embed transformation locally	yes: providing healthy diets while staying within the planetary boundaries	The One Planet network launched other programmes: consumer information on sus consumption, sus. Buildings & Construction, Sus. Lifestyles & Education, Sus. Public Procurement and Sus. Tourism

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Their key accomplishment is a multi-actor consensus, by industry as well as regional governments, NGOs or other stakeholders, that the food system is in need of a systemic approach when looking at new solutions. Here lies a great sustainability in the sense that solutions are not forced onto a system, but the stakeholders jointly discuss and build up those changes → the approach is highly inclusive and therefore likely to introduce sustainable and lasting changes

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

There is a strong focus on healthy and affordable diets - which 40% of global population cannot afford in 2020 leading to growing inequality due to growing power imbalances among food system actors - while respecting the planets boundaries. Food waste as a driver of food insecurity and unsustainability is also another key focus of the programme.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Awareness raising on food security and nutrition topics, building capacity and enable conditions for food systems to adapt sustainable practices, tools and methodologies to support governments in the transformation process and partnership building

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

inclusive, diverse, resilient, healthy and environmentally sustainable → a broad whole system approach to sustainability including health and equality

Main sources: <https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/programmes/sustainable-food-systems>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

Case 10: Organic Cities Europe, Europe

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Organic Cities Europe/Europe

One or two key features: network of organic cities → municipalities who advance on the topic of sustainable city food systems

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

Which ambitions and objectives: Umbrella organization for all organic cities in Europe; making their goals and ambitions visible on an international scale

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: In 2002 the network is founded in Italy with a focus on rural development and territories, a cultural model beyond merely agricultural cultivation, quality and artisanal production, regionalism and sustainability, education and food waste

What external input and output: builds up on the work of the european organic cities, therefore regional work can be seen as an input to the european network; outputs are events, talks and lobbying activities

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a *GAME*):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
European level; agricultural policy	organic cities representants (administration), local & european policy makers	Urban Food Systems	Networking; knowledge & experience exchange	Dependent on the existence and participation of local organic cities → dependence on local governments	Exchange on enhancing food system sustainability	On going since 2002 → over 20 years

Main sources: <https://www.sustainablefoodplaces.org/>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Connections to policymakers on an european level; voice on an european level	The actor is made up of sub-actors (regional organic cities) and therefore adapts to their activities and wishes; does not adapt to cities/actors unwilling to become an organic city	Actors form a network and trust the organic cities network with european representation	Defined goal is to: foster regional structures for organic production and procurement/ promoting & sharing best-practice in regional organic farming	The network works with european policymakers and the regional organic cities are implemented into the cities administration and therefore closely connected to all other departments → especially education departments for the topic of procurement

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The network is made up of several actors that present a different level of willingness to take action, also there are two further networks collected under the umbrella "Organic Cities Network Europe" which are the "Città del Bio" and the "BioStädte Netzwerk", who are very active in their own area. Therefore one might say the willingness of the actors is very high, but the actual european network does not have the resources or personnel to really work on topic-related projects, but is rather the organ for representation on an european level.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This case concentrates on the differences between regional organic and global conventional food production. In the networks view the unsustainable circumstances of the Food Systems are mostly global transportation, declining regional food security and growing practices of food not produced by ecological criteria.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The network mostly wants to promote the possibility of becoming a organic city to other cities, municipalities and regions. Organic Cities work - from the policymaker and administration side - on transforming the regional Food System in order to enhance the production and consumption of ecological foods. Also the network promotes the idea of the organic city movement to European & International Policymakers.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The indicator used here is the european label for organic food production and its criteria.

Main sources: <https://www.sustainablefoodplaces.org/>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

Case 11: Climate Smart Chefs, European Union

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Climate Smart Chefs

One or two key features: promotion of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running (01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

The LIFE CLIMATE SMART CHEFS is a European project receiving funding from the LIFE Programme of the European Union. It aims to contribute to the development and implementation of the EU Climate Policy and the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy. Project partners are one philanthropic funder, world's leading educational and training centre for the Italian food and beverage and hospitality sectors, the largest networks of Vocational Education and Training providers in Italy, a university, menu management software company.

Which ambitions and objectives:

The main project objectives are:

- To increase the awareness on the relationship between food and climate change at the EU level.
- To engage chefs as active changemakers and promoters of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets in the EU.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Thanks to the project's activities a Network of Life Climate Smart Chefs has been created made of chef associations, restaurants, hotels and caterers who will engage in the fight against food waste, reducing carbon emissions and water consumption.

What external input and output:

- the implementation of a high-level training course for chefs
- the development of a digital tool to design climate smart menus
- the creation of an Award dedicated to climate smart chefs and local initiatives promoting sustainable diets
- the creation of an EU Network of chef associations
- the implementation of the Life Climate Smart Chefs Vision 2030, a strategic paper aimed at providing policy recommendations and supporting EU Climate Policy.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diets	Vocational training institutes in the hospitality sectors, universities, IT companies, chef associations, restaurants, hotels and caterers.	An high-level training course, digital tools, an award, a strategic paper.	Creating a stable network of chefs working in restaurants and catering companies committed to food sustainability.	Make food businesses and their customers to make more informed and environmentally-conscious decision	Raising awareness among chefs on the importance of food sustainability and at the same time enhancing their skills and competencies in preparing healthy and sustainable menus.	Duration of the LIFE project: 01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024

Main sources: Climate Smart Chef project website

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
<p>Chefs are provided a training on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Why food is important for our planet's future and for solving climate change. - How to reduce food waste and save money - How to communicate the value of sustainability with your staff, suppliers and customersow to use a specially designed menu engineering tool to create menus that are healthy, affordable and good for the planet. 	<p>The training activities provided through this project are open to any chef interested in the topic despite its affiliation to a company or association part of the network.</p>	<p>The partnership sees very diverse partners from the vocational training, IT and hospitality sector coming together and share expertise/ develop skills.</p>	<p>The main goal is to provide turn chefs in active promoters of sustainable diets and encourage them to communicate and disseminate science-based information.</p>	<p>The project was able to mobilise caterers and chefs associations in one year. The challenge will be to maintain this mobilisation beyond the end of the project.</p>

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision-making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Within this projects, chefs are identified as potential active changemakers and promoters of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets in the EU.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Unsustainable and unhealthy diets in the hospitality sector.
Food loss and waste in the hospitality sector.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

One of the action, beyond the ones mentioned above, is the he implementation of the Life Climate Smart Chefs Vision 2030, a strategic paper aimed at providing policy recommendations.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The project is promoting the 'Foodprint' too is a fully automated, easy-to-use environmental impact scoring, display, and emission reporting system for the hospitality and food service (HaFS) sector. The aim is to combines the latest research with cutting-edge technology to support chefs and organisations on their journey to carbon neutrality .

Main sources: Climate Smart Chef project website

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP7

Case 12: EU Food Policy Coalition, European Union

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: EU Food Policy Coalition / Europe

One or two key features: Participants in the EU Food Policy Coalition work towards policy integration and alignment at the EU-level to facilitate the transition to sustainable food systems. The Coalition provides the debating space to discuss policies and, sometimes, carry out joint activities.

Status: Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Coalition brings together civil society and organisations working towards refining and advocating for a shared vision of sustainable food systems at the EU level such as: NGOs from a broad spectrum working on food systems, grassroots social movements, farmers organisations, organisations of fishers, trade unions, think tanks, scientific and research groups.

Which ambitions and objectives: Participants in the EU Food Policy Coalition work towards policy integration and alignment at the EU-level to facilitate the transition to sustainable food systems. The Coalition provides the debating space to discuss policies and, sometimes, carry out joint activities.

What external input and output: The report [Towards a Common Food Policy for the EU](#), captures the objectives and priorities co-constructed by a wide range of actors, and constitutes the document that crystallises the overarching policy vision of the Coalition.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Transition to sustainable food systems	NGOs from a broad spectrum working on food systems, grassroots social movements, farmers organisations, organisations of fishers, trade unions, think tanks, scientific and research groups.	The Coalition provides the debating space to discuss policies and, sometimes, carry out joint activities.	Participants in the Coalition work towards policy integration and alignment at the EU-level to facilitate the transition to sustainable food systems.	An integrated food policy can reclaim public policy for the public good, rebuild public confidence in the European project, and put the EU on track to meet the SDGs and the Paris Climate Agreement.	Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections, endorsed by 26 organisations + Open letter on the need for a strong proposal on an EU legislative framework for sustainable food systems, endorsed by 286 organisations	Short, medium and long term

Main sources: <https://foodpolicycoalition.eu/about-us/>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Broad coalition bringing together different actors.	Flexible, the coalition provides the debating space to discuss policy, and take joint activities.	Different actors involved, NGOs, Grassroots social movements, farmers organizations, think tanks, trade unions, research groups	Involved actors can decide autonomously whether to endorse the outputs that have emerged from internal debates (e.g. Elections Manifesto – Our Food, Our Health, Our Planet)	Closely linked to biodiversity loss, climate change and social justice but no joint objectives with other clusters

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Actors are involved, as seen by the high number of endorsement, 286, for the open letter on the need for a strong proposal on an EU legislative framework for sustainable food systems.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Food systems are pushing us across 'planetary boundaries', driving diet-related diseases and failing to deliver decent livelihoods in the EU and beyond: they are therefore at the heart of the change that citizens are asking for. EU policies, and in particular the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), have so far failed to drive a transition towards sustainable food systems.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

- March 2023: Elections Manifesto – Our Food, Our Health, Our Planet
- February 2023: Open letter on the need for a strong proposal on an EU legislative framework for sustainable food systems
- October 2022: Manifesto for establishing Minimum Standards for Public Canteens across the EU

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Inclusive, transparent, socially and economically just food system

Main sources: <https://foodpolicycoalition.eu/about-us/>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP7

Case 13: The Sustainable Restaurant Association, United Kingdom

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country The Sustainable Restaurant Association, United Kingdom

One or two key features: The SRA believes food service businesses can have a restorative impact on the planet.

Status: Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: To accelerate change towards an environmentally restorative and socially progressive hospitality sector, the SRA works with businesses from across foodservice, as well as like-minded industry bodies, campaign groups and businesses that supply the sector through its signature programme, Food Made Good.

Which ambitions and objectives: Bring together progressive people working in the food sector & empower them to change the system faster.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Sitting at the intersection between foodservice and the sustainable food movement, the SRA defines sustainability for the sector, assesses behavior, measures action and celebrates progress.

What external input and output: The Food Made Good online community is a thriving space where businesses can connect to seek solutions for their sustainability challenges, share successes and communicate with like-minded individuals who are committed to meeting the same goals. Issue specific conversations and threads, alongside the portfolio of accompanying tools and resources provide users with a genuine depth of support on their journey.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Accelerate change toward an environmentally restorative and socially progressive hospitality sector.	Foodservice providers.	<i>Food Made Good</i> is the most globally recognised industry standard for measuring sustainability across the Hospitality Sector.	Promotes and measures action through the industry standard sustainability certification, the Food Made Good Rating + Encourage best practice and inspire healthy competition.	Being part of a global movement and working together with other foodservice providers to build a more sustainable future.	What began as a membership organisation with 50 founding members has grown into a global movement of more than 10,000 kitchens. It is a very diverse community of food service businesses, from high end to high street, from street-food staples to workplace canteens, from independent cafes to Michelin starred restaurants, all working to make sustainability part of their DNA.	Short, medium and long term.

Main sources: <https://thesra.org/our-aims/>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SRA provides continual support to advance foodservice businesses environmental and social responsibility	Flexible, actors adapt their strategies to achieve the sustainability objectives laid out in the 'Food Made Good' framework	Actors act individually, but they are intrinsically part of a wider movement with the opportunity for each actors to connect and seek solutions for their sustainability challenges	Goal is already laid out in the 'Food Made Good' framework	Food retailers and Food suppliers working jointly

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The rapid increase in membership, which now exceeds 10,000, is evidence of the growing involvement of foodservice providers.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Greenhouse gas emissions from meat and dairy production, food waste, single-use plastic.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

SRA aims to accelerate change towards a food sector that is socially progressive and environmentally restorative by connecting progressive people and businesses both in the UK and across the globe through the Food Made Good programme.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

- Number of foodservice providers joining the 'Food Made Good' programme
- Improvements in 'sustainable rating' of foodservice providers over time

Main sources: <https://thesra.org/our-aims/>

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP7

Case 14: Semences Paysannes, France

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Réseau Semences Paysannes, France

One or two key features: Promotion of biodiversity

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

Which ambitions and objectives: The association aims to bring together and network the actors of cultivated biodiversity to promote the dissemination of farmers' seeds and associated know-how, develop and promote their dynamic management in farms and gardens, as well as implement any other actions that can contribute to it.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The association has a board: [Organigramme RSP \(semencespaysannes.org\)](http://Organigramme RSP (semencespaysannes.org)). Members of the association are National farmers organisations, Producers associations, associations working on biodiversity preservation, artisanal seed growers, etc.

What external input and output: Wide awareness raising activities, ad hoc training, information sessions promotion of local initiatives.

[Réseau Semences Paysannes - L'association](#)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Peasants' seeds as key element to maintain cultivated biodiversity essential to our food.	Peasants	Events, trainings, meetings, legal advice.		I.e. national reform of seeds at European level or GMO regulation.	For example: In 2021 more than 100 training were delivered. Annual 'organisation of 'Semain des Semences Paysannes', creation'	The network exists since 2003.

Main sources: [Réseau Semences Paysannes - L'association](#)

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The group provides trainings and organise awareness raising activities (i.e. Semaine de semences paysannes). Legal advice is provided. Ad hoc thematic working groups on the different types of seeds have been established.		National farmers organisations, Producers associations, associations working on biodiversity preservation, artisanal seed growers.	Promotion and commercialisation of traditional seeds.	Lawyers.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The association is actively promoting through its activities social and ecological agriculture rooted in the territories.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The industry's radical monopoly on seeds has led to the disappearance of 75% of cultivated biodiversity in 50 years

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Safeguarding and dissemination of vegetable and fruit varieties and local cereals, but also grass species; Organization of national and international meetings, trips study to exchange seeds and know-how; Legal watch to decipher the evolutions of a context binding regulations and policies for farmers' seeds; Participatory selection projects to safeguard and select suitable population-varieties organic and peasant farming; Training to transmit and spread knowledge and know-how around cultivated biodiversity.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

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Main sources: [Réseau Semences Paysannes - L'association](#)

Case 15: Eating Better, United Kingdom

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Eating Better, United Kingdom

One or two key features: Growing network to accelerate a shift to a sustainable and healthier food system, with “less and better” meat and more plants.

Status: Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The power of the alliance comes from its breadth, diversity and expertise. From environmental and animal welfare charities to public health and social justice, Eating Better is working to create a fair and sustainable food environment, where everyone has access to healthy, affordable and nutritious food. The focus is ‘less and better’ meat and more plants, which is better for humanity, for nature and for the planet.

Which ambitions and objectives: Eating Better’s goal is to halve meat and dairy consumption in the UK by the end of this crucial decade of action to reduce GHG emissions, protect nature and get us all eating better.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Eating Better raise funds for its work from supporter organisations, trusts, foundations, and individuals. It does not seek or accept funds directly from commercial organisations. Trustees are responsible for approving all major grant applications.

What external input and output: Eating Better draws on the experience and expertise of the alliance to accelerate transformational change in the way society produces and consumes food. Eating Better works across the food system from farm to table, collaborating with and influencing civil society, local and central government, food retail, food service, farmers, academia and investors. Collectively and collaboratively the alliance works to make food part of the solution to the climate, nature and health crises.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
The Eating Better alliance is working to stimulate a 50% reduction in meat and dairy consumption in the UK by 2030, and for a transition to ‘better’ meat and dairy as standard.	Government, Producers, Food retail, Food service, Investors.	A roadmap to less and better meat and dairy, providing 24 actions to be taken across 5 sectors to create an enabling environment to drive the necessary transformation in eating habits.	24 actions to be taken across 5 sectors – e.g. (I) Deliver a cross-departmental food and farming strategy; (II) Harness opportunities for more plant production; (III) Embed a sustainable diets strategy across the business; (IV) Put more plants on plates and menus; (V) Engage to promote healthy and sustainable production.	Through data-driven reports and analysis of food trends Eating Better tracks progress, calling out inaction and demand more of those lagging behind in promoting sustainable and balanced diets.	In 2022, Eating Better made great strides to improve understanding of the food system, track progress, influence the agenda for change, grow the alliance and to showcase positive practices in producing and serving less and better meat and dairy in line with the Better by Half roadmap.	Short, medium and long-term, with the aim of stimulating a 50% reduction in meat and dairy consumption in the UK by 2030.

Main sources: <https://eating-better.org/>

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food|paths

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Clear actions are provided by Eating Better to accelerate the transition from producing and eating too much meat and dairy to a fairer, healthier and more sustainable food system.	Flexible, Eating Better is regularly reaching out to new stakeholders to grow in influence, and to bring new voices into the alliance.	The alliance brings together a wide array of actors from different sectors.	The alliance members collectively and collaborative work to make food part of the solution to the climate, nature and health crisis.	Works with other Partner Networks such as the 'European Public Health Alliance' or the 'Food Research Collaboration'.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Eating Better's survey on retailer tactic around meat found that the retailers are not matching their rhetoric on sustainable eating with action to reduce meat productions.

Another surveys highlighted that 86% of members have used Eating Better's resources to support their work over the last two years.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Food systems are associated with roughly 42% of global greenhouse gas emissions according to the IPP WG3, April 2022 report, with livestock farming a major contributor. Meat from ruminants such as sheep and cows have the highest GHG intensity. Moreover, producing meat and dairy takes up swathes of land with half of the world's habitable land being used for agriculture with more than three-quarters of this used for livestock production, while contributing only 37% of the protein in the global food supply. Intensive agriculture is the also the biggest driver of habitat and wildlife loss, while crowded conditions for farmed animals are potential breeding grounds for dangerous pathogens and emerging pandemics, risking public health.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Eating Better works across the food system from farm to table, collaborating with and influencing civil society, local and central government, food retail, food service, farmers, academia and investors. It has developed the 'Better By Half' roadmap, which identifies 24 actions across five influential sectors, where change needs to happen to ensure everyone has access to healthy, nutritious and affordable food.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Numbers of supporting organisations and partner networks; digital engagement (e.g. hours watched on YouTube, website visitors, LinkedIn views).

Main sources: <https://eating-better.org/>

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Case 16: Mit Eszel platform, Hungary

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Mit Eszel? platform/ Hungary
One or two key features: Farm sustainability assessment system and consumer information platform
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Based on the AgriToolKit sustainability tool, Mit Eszel? platform was developed as an interactive, customer-supported, quality assurance system. The Agri Toolkit was developed by Agri Kulti in collaboration with farmers and consumers. As a group of environmental consultants and innovators, Agrikulti has more than 10 years of experience with natural and social science research and development of sustainable food systems, farmers markets, farmers and consumers.

Which ambitions and objectives: The most important goal is to strengthen city-rural relations by building short supply chains that are both ecologically and economically viable. Mit Eszel? trademark was registered in order to provide customers with information about sustainably operating farms. The platform also aims to encourage consumers to visit nearby farms to interact with the producers of their food and better understand where the food they eat comes from and how its production affects the environment around us. Agri Toolkit is a science based, complex and easy to interpret farming sustainability assessment tool. The system considers farming activities and does not measure physical, chemical or biological outcome variables. The Green Test is the consumer friendly version developed for farm visits.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: AgriKulti is a small non-profit company and social enterprise. It participates in European research, innovation and coordination actions. AgriKulti has launched a number of innovative initiatives to build

What external input and output: AgriKulti has received funding from EU projects and the Hungarian Ministry of Agriculture to develop the AgriToolKit and the Mit Eszel? platform. The AgriToolKit indicators are based on the FAO's Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems (SAFA) guidelines. AgriKulti issues certificates for farms that pass the evaluation.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Hungary is experiencing significant rural to urban migration, with a major cause being rural unemployment	Farmers, Consumers, Researchers, Environmentalists	Fresh vegetables, Pulses, Ancient cereals	Innovations: Nagymaros Farmers Market Házikó farm-to-table restaurant/factory	National agroecology policy – promoting traditional varieties and breeds EU Organic standard	Functioning farmers market in the centre of Budapest Lessons learned about economic sustainability from Farm-to-table restaurant (40 farmers served 300 partners, 12 employees) New living lab on neglected legumes	2010 – AgriKulti created 2011 – Nagymaros Farmers market started 2014-2018 - Házikó running 2020 – AgriToolKit + Green Test

Main sources: <https://agritoolkit.eu/index.html> ; <https://mitesz.hu/>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
AgriKulti – knowledge about sustainable food systems	Flexible – Adapting to different innovations and opportunities to create sustainable food systems	Networked domestically and internationally (EU)	Yes – working on a definition of agroecology for Senegal	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
Consumers Association (Association of Conscious Consumers (ACC)/Hungarian Tudatos Vásárlók Egyesülete (TVE)) – consumer knowledge/demand	Flexible –consumer campaigns and behaviour change programs to support solidarity based food systems	Cluster of consumers, but networked with farmers and advisors	Yes – healthy diets for the Senegalese	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
Farmers – traditional knowledge and organic knowledge	Flexible – adapts to climate and market pressures	Clustered through local chapters of farmer groups	Sometimes – not all farmers have the same goal	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
Ministry of Agriculture – political will and financing of short circuit food chains	Semi-flexible – adapts to include agroecology and local food systems into national policy	Networked with the researcher experts and the EU	Sometimes – the government seeks to reduce unemployment and increase food sovereignty	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
European Union - funding	Flexible – EU funding of research opens more avenues for innovation	Networked across the EU	Yes – EU Green Deal and SDGs	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

AgriKulti has been leading, and at times following, their partners through a number of experimentations and innovations seeking to create local food systems that link Budapest with the surrounding rural areas. Their status as a social enterprise and their willingness to risk personal private and public funds to advance the ideas demonstrates a strong feeling of responsibility for changing current food systems.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The challenges of a lack of national food sovereignty and rural unemployment were the original drivers of the need to change the Food System. The promotion of agroecology and the support for traditional breeds and agrobiodiversity by the Ministry of Agriculture has offered a means for local innovators to become more active. The Covid crisis and the Russian-Ukrainian war have highlighted the importance of strengthening the resilience and autonomy of food systems, particularly in Eastern Europe. The lack of diversity in both agriculture and markets have revealed the unsustainability of food systems in Hungary.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

AgriKulti is but one actor within an expanding network of innovators who are testing new ways of linking farmers and consumers. The approach, which is based on linking scientific knowledge with farmers' knowledge and consumers' knowledge has brought these actors into closer collaboration. The development of metrics, simple evaluations and labels enable greater transparency about the origin of food in Budapest.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The evaluation system takes into account the economic decisions. Specifically, the diversity of cultivated varieties, the impact of farming technologies on wildlife, the climate, and the soil; material and energy use, animal welfare and water use, and the impact on the local economy. The initiative contributes to SDGs 2, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 15.

Main sources: <https://agritoolkit.eu/index.html> ; <https://mitesz.el.hu/>

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Case 17: Dynamics for an Agroecological Transition in Senegal (DyTAES), Senegal

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Dynamics for an Agroecological Transition in Senegal (DyTAES) / Senegal

One or two key features: National multi-stakeholder network that is driven by farmers and researchers.

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The "Dynamics for an Agroecological Transition in Senegal" (DyTAES) is a network that was created in 2019. It brings together organizations of producers, consumers, rural women, NGOs, research institutions, civil society networks, a network of local elected officials and companies. An annual Caravan that carried out workshops across all agroecological zones enabled a co-creation of the national platform and national level policy recommendations. Because of the interest of Mayors and local officials, and thanks to the decentralisation of the state more broadly, DyTAELs (local dynamics) began to be formed in 2021 and represent the future focus of the DyTAES.

Which ambitions and objectives: DyTAES has the aim of promoting an agroecological transition in Senegal through advocacy, awareness-raising, sharing of experience and support for territories in transition.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The DyTAES is made up of colleges representing the different stakeholder groups nationally and in each territory.

What external input and output: The diagnostic analysis and the political recommendations delivered to the Ministers of Agriculture and the Environment were developed based on a participatory consultation process that included more than 1.000 actors from 6 agroecological zones of Senegal (territorial workshops) and from Dakar (consumer workshops). The process has been supported by French and Senegalese researchers, European donors and intergovernmental organisations (ECOWAS and FAO).

Figure 2 - Les 10 éléments clés de l'agroécologie. Le DyTAES a favorisé la prise de conscience de ces éléments. Les principes de l'agroécologie favorisent les actions au niveau local et global.

Figure 6 - Vue d'ensemble des liens entre les 10 éléments de l'agroécologie et les 15 défis de l'agriculture sénégalaise.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
First Government of Macky Sall named the "agroecological transition" the third pillar of its political programme Public controversies around pesticides poisoning	Farmers Orgs, international and national NGOs, French and national research institutes, Donors, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environment, FAO	Fresh vegetables (onions, carrots, cabbage, eggplants), 'agroecological technical packages', knowledge	Farmer training, Creation of a national platform, Creation of local platforms, Agroecological Caravan, Annual Agroecology Day, Agroecology restaurant in Thies, Box schemes	Government decentralization (Agriculture and Environment Advisors at District level) Organic manure included in government subsidies ECOWAS and FAO 10 programme planning on agroecology	National platform that includes all stakeholders Local platforms for local action Ongoing multi-stakeholder policy dialogue Topic specific policy briefs	2019 – creation of the DyTAES 2021 – creation of the first DyTAEL 2023 – 3 rd caravan

Main sources: <https://dytaes.sn>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Researchers – knowledge about agroecology	Flexible – Adapting to different agro-ecological zones	Networked domestically and internationally (EU)	Yes – working on a definition of agroecology for Senegal	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Consumers Association (CICODEV) – consumer demand	Flexible – adapting consumer campaigns to healthy and agroecological food	Cluster of consumers, but networked with NGOs	Yes – healthy diets for the Senegalese	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
CNCR (Farmers Union) – traditional knowledge and political influence	Flexible – adapts to climate and market pressures	Clustered through local chapters of farmer groups	Sometimes – not all farmers have the same goal	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Ministries of Agriculture and Environment – political will	Semi-flexible – adapts to include the DyTAES in a policy dialogue, but dependent on government policy	Networked with the researcher experts, Donors, Farmers Union and NGOs	Sometimes – the government seeks to reduce food insecurity and adapt to climate-change. Agroecology is seen as 'reforestation'	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
NGOs – complementary projects, knowledge	Semi-flexible – combines interest for some common advocacy, but competes for donor funding	Networked within DyTAES	Sometimes – not all NGOs share the same mission and have different visions of agroecology	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Donors - funding	Inflexible – Donor funding is tied to donor priorities	Usually 1-1 interactions	No – each donor has its own goal in line with its national/organisational strategy	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Private sector – markets, legitimacy	Flexible – New markets for bioinputs emerging	Clustered , but not organised in an interprofession	Sometimes – they will also sell agrochemicals and junk food	Maybe – it depends on the interests of each company

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The remarkable aspect of the DyTAES (and the DyTAELs) is that all of the actors have assumed responsibility for a sustainability transition. The co-creation process that is inclusive not just of all types of actors, but also of all agroecological zones across the country is promising. The annual caravan offers a strong model for regional consultations.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The challenges of a lack of food sovereignty and youth unemployment in a context of climate change is the core circumstance of unsustainability. Faced with the widespread degradation of natural resources (water, soil, forests, etc.), agroecology makes it possible to rethink in depth our ways of producing, exchanging and consuming in order to build a new development model. The Covid crisis and the Russian-Ukrainian war have highlighted the importance of strengthening the resilience and autonomy of food systems.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Farmer and consumer empowerment in policy dialogues. There are significant investments in research, innovation and training in agroecology that are funded by the European Commission (in particular as well as other donors). The consumer demand for pesticide-free food is growing substantially in the capital city (Dakar).

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Diversity, Equity and inclusion of women, youth and smallholder farmers. They have created their own evaluation framework based on 15 major challenges that cover natural resources, family farming and sustainable agri-food systems. The initiative contributes to SDGs 2, 11, 12, 13, 15.

Main sources: <https://dytaes.sn>

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Case 18: Etiquettable, France

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Etiquettable / France
One or two key features: Digital app using consumer feedback and LCA-based scores
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Created by two innovators (a climate educator and a climate engineer) from different backgrounds in 2009, eCO2 received funding from the French ecological transition agency (ADEME) in 2017, to create the Etiquettable mobile application. As part of the work put into developing the app, eCO2 created a collective of sustainable consumption actors – Yuka, ScanUp, Open Food Facts, FrigoMagic, La Fourche, FoodChéri, marmiton and SeaZon – to develop Eco-score®. Eco-score® uses Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [based on the Agribalyse® database] to give a score about the environmental sustainability of food

Which ambitions and objectives: Design and implement actions aimed at accelerating the ecological transition through changes in behaviour. In particular, they offer awareness-raising programmes aimed at local communities. Etiquettable aims to contribute to a more sustainable diet and seeks to bring together disparate information on cooking, the environment and nutrition. It therefore offers multi-functional services in one: a list of seasonal fruit and vegetables as well as nutrition information, endangered fish species, sustainable recipes to share and rate, geolocation of committed restaurants, sustainable cooking tips and various other information.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: eCO2 is social enterprise « Entreprise Solidaire d'Utilité Sociale » and Eco-score® is a collective of social enterprises. Eco-score® is a registered trademark protected by ADEME since 2020. Usage licenses have been granted to organizations performing ratings, on a temporary and transitional basis pending future regulations (Climate and Resilience Law 2021).

What external input and output: The app was user-driven in its design (users tested the app at different stages of development) and it includes recipes and tips from chefs committed to sustainable cooking. Underlying this app there is an impact and recipe sourcing calculation, which is based on the food databases of the French Food Safety and Environment authorities. A scientific committee works with the developers to conduct continuous food impact assessments and research on the impact of public information and communication about nutrition and environmental qualities of food. The application is interactive and allows all users to add new food, tips, recipes, restaurant reviews, etc. that builds the community trust.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
The Grenelle de l'environnement (an open multi-party debate in 2007) introduced environmental labelling in 2009 The EU Green Deal encourages eco-labelling	Environmental consultants Civil Society Organisations Ecological Transition Agency Private labels	Sustainability information, eco-scores, ethical restaurant labels, consumer ratings	A digital app that facilitates the access to this information Consumer feedback and rating of restaurants and vendors	Voluntary eco-labelling since 2013 Circular Economy Road map 2018 Article 15 of Law n° 2020-105 to protect against Waste and to promote the circular economy 2023 Eco-labelling should be obligatory	Increased use of the app (>2%/year) Increased coverage (5892 producers & shops in 2023, >24% since 2021; 1263 restaurants, >26% since 2021)	2009 – eCO2 created 2017 – Etiquettable launched 2020 – Eco-score registered with ADEME 2023 – Eco-score official ADEME eco-label

Main sources: <https://etiquettable.eco2initiative.com/>

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
eCO2 – knowledge about LCA	Flexible – Adapting the app to consumer feedback	Networked domestically	Yes – working on the Eco-Score in a collective	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Place to Bio – geolocalisation of organic and responsible restaurants	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – organic and responsible restaurants	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Bon pour le climat – lists eco-calculated recipes	Flexible – adapts their information based on Etiquettable	Networked domestically	Yes – sustainable ingredients	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
CartoVrac – references bulk goods stores from OpenStreetMap	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – sustainable ingredients	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Ecotable and FIG – certify (maintain lists of) restaurants according to a standard for eco-responsibility	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – responsible restaurants	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Vegoresto – maintains a list of vegan or vegan-friendly restaurants	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – vegan restaurants	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Ethic Ocean – synthesizes knowledge about seafood	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – protection of marine biodiversity	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Government Agency (ADEME) – legitimizes and finances the innovation	Flexible - is mediating between government and the social actors	Networked domestically	Yes – to guide the ecological transition	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

All of the private actors are mission-driven social enterprises or NGOs. Their individual and collective missions are to participate in changing how food is produced and consumed. ADEME is making significant investments so to implement mandatory eco-labelling.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The unsustainability of current diets – particularly related to food waste, biodiversity loss and low levels of consumption of (in season) vegetables.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

With the Etiquettable app, and with the accompanying Eco-score® and ratings on restaurants and sales points, consumers are better informed about where they can eat more sustainably. Consumers are also engaged by contributing to the online maps and reporting those restaurants and sales points that are not delivering on their sustainability promise.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Reduction of food waste, sustainable packaging, biodiversity, transparency and origin of ingredients, seasonality of ingredients, certified production, product environmental footprint (LCA). The initiative contributes to SDGs 2, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15.

Main sources: <https://etiquettable.eco2initiative.com/>

Case 19: Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean (SFS-MED) platform, Italy

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: SFS-MED Platform (Italy)

One or two key features: The SFS-MED Platform is a multi-stakeholder initiative aimed at promoting collaborative actions for the sustainable transformation of food systems in the Mediterranean, ultimately accelerating progress on the delivery of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in the region.

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The founding members began circulating the idea with the OPN-SFSP in 2018, which culminated in the organization of the 2nd World Conference on the Revitalization of the Mediterranean Diet on “Strategies towards More Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean Region. The Mediterranean Diet as a Lever Bridging Consumption and Production in a Sustainable and Healthy Way”, held in Palermo, in May 2019. A MOU was signed between CIHEAM, FAO and UfMS in January 2021 and two food system dialogues were held in preparation for the UNFSS and the 3rd World Conference on Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean.

Which ambitions and objectives: The platform aims to be forum for dialogue and collaboration on priority themes for sustainable food systems in the Mediterranean, acting as a neutral facilitator of multi-stakeholder exchange to enhance policy coherence, build trust, and promote the effective implementation of actions.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Created in 2021 by the International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies (CIHEAM), the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN (FAO), the Union for the Mediterranean (UfMS) and the Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA), it is a network for strengthening knowledge sharing and capacity building related to sustainable food consumption and production across the Mediterranean.

What external input and output: The platform aims to rebalance sustainability and finance. Dedicated support for the co-creation of flagship projects and investment proposals will enable actors in Mediterranean food systems to access funding and scale up sustainable investments. The platform catalyses regional cooperation for data sharing, science diplomacy, and the advancement of green and blue practices, as well as inclusive and digital innovation

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
The Mediterranean diet is threatened by climate change and changing food habits	Researchers, public policy-makers, funding agencies, NGOs, consumers organizations	Knowledge, investments, digital technologies	Co-creation of flagship projects, investment proposals, data sharing, scientific diplomacy	Forum for dialogue and collaboration on 5 themes (that will be revisited periodically)	3 webinars per year on priority topics, the bi-yearly conference on the Mediterranean Diet, Communities of Practice, Funding co-creation projects (tbd)	2019 – 2 nd World Conference on the Mediterranean Diet 2021 – MOU establishing the SFS-MED

Main sources: <https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/programmes/sustainable-food-systems/sfs-med-platform>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
CIHEAM – scientific knowledge production	Flexible – has adapted research to challenges of climate change	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they are part of the OPN-SFSP and UNFSS Coalitions
FAO – international knowledge broker	Flexible – has included the EU Mediterranean region in its programme	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they are part of the OPN-SFSP and UNFSS Coalitions
UFMS – governments of Member States	Flexible – new collaborations in the region	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they are part of intergovernmental groups in EU and AU
PRIMA – funding mechanism for innovation	Flexible – opportunities for funding co-creation and innovation	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they collaborate with EU research networks

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

With the creation of this new regional platform, the actors have changed the way in which they make decisions about the funding of investments for SFS. The collaboration among State governments, research and innovation donors and the research institutes offers an interesting example for the EU Partnership for SFS.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

There are four pillars of unsustainable circumstances in the food system that the platform presented in this case is addressing. In terms of environmental unsustainability, the Mediterranean region is suffering from over fishing, insufficient water resources, and unsustainable sources of energy. The current rates of unemployment and economic inequalities between northern and southern Mediterranean countries are unsustainable. Migration in the Mediterranean basin and gender inequalities exacerbate unsustainable lifestyles. Finally, urbanization and the nutrition transition are threatening the Mediterranean diet – which is largely based on legumes, vegetables, fruits and whole grains.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Knowledge creation, sharing and new collaborations are emerging within this platform. The platform is preparing to support investment projects in sustainable blue and green economies, as well as in efforts to support the production and consumption of food products that are foundations of the Mediterranean diet.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Diversity, inclusion and equity are key aspects of the food systems that are being promoted. Specifically, the platform is measuring its contributions to SDG 2, 12 (12.1, 12.2, 12.3, 12.8), 17.

Main sources: <https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/programmes/sustainable-food-systems/sfs-med-platform>

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Case 20: The Sustainable Food Systems Program (SPNF-PKKKY) Himachal Pradesh, India

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country ...The Sustainable Food Systems Program (SPNF-PKKKY) Himachal Pradesh / India
One or two key features: ...Training programme for producers to adopt natural farming, evaluation and certification system for local and public markets **Status** (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Development of **Framework for Sustainable Food System Platform for Natural Farming (SuSPNF)**, which is an innovative self-assessment farmers' certification methodology. Based on an innovative fellowship between the state government of Himachal Pradesh and the Farmers and Producers Organizations of natural farmers. Inspired by Subhash Palekar Father of Natural Farming Method.

Which ambitions and objectives: Captive outlets for target selling of natural farming produce; Canopies and other local promotion means for natural farming farmers; Logos and Branding of the natural produce of the state.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The project was originally all run out of the State government's Agriculture office's State Project Implementation unit (SPIU). In 2022, a boutique was opened to sell certified products in the State capital city. Since 2023, partnership forged with the Dr. YS Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry to develop training on natural farming and sustainable food systems.

What external input and output: Knowledge sharing with Zero Budget Natural Farming in Andhra Pradesh, FAO-INRAE handbook for innovators on sustainable food systems and e-learning course. PGSOC, a private, national level organic participatory guarantee system. IFOAM Organics International

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
State level programme to transition all farmers in the state to natural farming	State government, Natural farmers, University, Farm advisors, Public shop	Apples, horticulture crops, wild collected crops, processed products	Adoption of Natural farming practices 3 * Certification scheme	Bilingual Default Access for new farmers (1*) Fast in response with a set time frame Perpetual Status for farmers (unless system-triggered) Peer Review Public Domain - Checks and Balances	Inclusion of most farmers in the State. Notable reduction in synthetic inputs Reduction in the costs of farming	Officially launched in 2018 No end date in sight

Main sources: www.spnfh.in

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
State government – financial incentives and label	Flexible - has accepted innovative forms of certification	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	With other States and federal government
Natural farmers – farming practices, peer reviews	Flexible – has changed farming practice	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	With other farmers to form peer groups
University – training	Flexible - has developed new curricula	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	With national and international researchers
Computer scientists - digital platform, transparency	Flexible – adapting platform to fit needs	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	No
Public shop – market access	Flexible – adapting to public and private market quality criteria	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	No

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

This initiative emerged from dialogues that had been going on in the State for many years about the need to reduce pesticides use in order to improve the health of farmers. The government collaborated with the University, consultants, external researchers and computer scientists in order to study and then develop a certification system that would meet the needs of the farmers and ensure that the products could be sold and consumed within the state and external to the state.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The first element is an unsustainable use of pesticides in agriculture and the health and food safety concerns that accompany it. The second element is the unsustainable cost of industrial farming. Third, the case addresses the unsustainable export of produce outside of the state and encourages the consumption of diversified production within the state.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The first action is training of farmers in natural farming practices through the public extension system. The second is the development of an evaluation and certification system that enables farmers to progress from their point of entry at 1* to full achievement of natural farming at 3*. 2* and 3* farmers can use the SPNF seal. 3* farmers have access to the official marketing channels of the program and additional state incentives.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The core indicators are related to the use of off-farm sourced inputs. A mapping against the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has been completed and the SPNF-HP program has been found to contribute to 7 of the 17 SDGs (addressing 15 targets and 18 indicators). Specifically: 1 (1.4), 2 (2.3, 2.4, 2.5), 6 (6.4), 8 (8.3, 8.9), 9 (9.3), 12 (12.1, 12.3, 12.6, 12.7) and 15 (15.3, 15.4, 15.9)

Main sources: www.spnfhp.in

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

Case 21: Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM), Tanzania

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM) / Tanzania

One or two key features: National multi-stakeholder platform that represents the Organic sector and governs the use of the East African Organic Products Standards in Tanzania

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM) is a registered NGO formed in 2005 under the NGO Act of 2002. They are an umbrella organization that coordinates and promotes the development of organic farming among farmers, distributors and consumers through networking and information distribution.

Which ambitions and objectives: TOAM sees development of the organic farming sector as a crucial factor for sustainable livelihoods and envisions establishing a vibrant, sustainable and mutually beneficial organic sector in Tanzania.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: TOAM has a secretariat with >10 full time employees and is governed by a Board of Directors, led by a Chairperson. They are a member-based organization and count 115 members. These members include various types of institutions and organizations such as farmers associations and cooperatives, NGOs, organic operators, companies, distributors, researchers and trainers.

What external input and output: TOAM exists to provide capacity building on organic practices, quality management for compliance to organic standards, improvement to value chains, lobbying and advocating for supportive policies, and information collection and distribution. TOAM provides and distributes information on organic food to its members and other stakeholders in the whole of Tanzania.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Organic sector focused almost exclusively on export and a domestic agriculture policy focused on green revolution technologies. Yet a growing domestic consumer interest in sustainability	Farmers Orgs, national NGOs, Certifiers, Donors, Sokoine University, Participatory Guarantee Systems (PGS) Ministries of Agriculture and Trade	Tropical fruits, seasonal vegetables, Spices, coffee, cosmetics, knowledge	Farmer training, Creation of PGS, National accreditation for the Kilimo Hai label, Policy advocacy, Consumer awareness and rural radio	Regional standard for organic agriculture Third-party and PGS certification authorized New Training Centre of Excellence, with an Organic programme planned	4 th largest number of Organic certified farms in the World Organic agriculture strategy finalised in 2023	2005: Creation of TOAM 2007: Creation of East African Kilimo Hai Mark 2017: One stop shop for TZ organic created 2023: Organic Sector strategy

Main sources: <https://kilimohai.org/>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
TOAM – knowledge about organic certification	Flexible – TOAM adapts to the ministry and its members	Networked domestically and on the continent	Yes – common mission and values for the organization	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
TOAM Board – political alliances and legitimacy	Flexible – adapts to the ministry and TOAM members	Networked on the continent	Yes – common mission and values for the organization	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
Farmer members – knowledge about organic agriculture	Flexible – adapts to climate and market pressures	Clusters through farmer groups and PGS	Sometimes – not all farmers have the same goal	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
Ministry of Agriculture – political will	Semi-flexible – adapts to TOAM advocacy, but dependent on government policy	Networked with TOAM and Donors	Sometimes – the government seeks to reduce food insecurity and adapt to climate-change	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
NGO members – complementary projects, knowledge	Semi-flexible – combines interest for some common advocacy, but competes for donor funding	Networked within TOAM	Sometimes – not all NGOs share the same mission and have different visions of sustainability	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
Donors - funding	Inflexible – Donor funding is tied to donor priorities	Usually 1-1 interactions	No – each donor has its own goal in line with its national/organizational strategy (not always organic)	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

All of the actors in this case recognize that they have a role to play in the sustainability transition of their food system. While there is not full government support for organic agriculture in the country, the recent policy advances recognizes the importance of organic in creating sustainable food systems in the country. TOAM is a forum of stakeholders in the organic sector. It creates platforms for larger and louder voices for influencing policy makers and practitioners on adoption of best practices in the organic sector. There are a handful of donors who are also committed to supporting the transition of local food systems towards sustainability.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Capital intensive agriculture is not sustainable for the majority of smallholder farmers, who are increasingly being excluded from the food system. The increased use in pesticides has had negative effects on farmer worker health and chemical residues on food in the local markets are increasing. The dependence on export markets for organic products creates risks for the resilience of the domestic market, where demand is growing rapidly for healthy food.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

TOAM is taking action on food, nutrition and health by increasing the awareness of food consumers on health benefits of organic foods. TOAM empowers smallholder farmers to take control of their seed security and take back control over their food systems by reclaiming their food sovereignty. TOAM promotes the relevance of Organic Agriculture on environmental management, climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation. TOAM fosters gender equitable access and benefits of organic value chains outcomes by empowering women and youth on decision making and control on organic farming systems and utilization. TOAM generates evidence on how, where and through which value chains, organic farming can offer alternative sustainable livelihoods strategies. TOAM takes custodianship of branding and certification ensuring visibility, recognition, and credibility of organic commodities in the market.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Diversity, Equity and inclusion of women, youth and smallholder farmers. They measure the number of certified farmers and the value of the domestic market. The initiative contributes to SDGs 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 17.

Main sources: <https://kilimohai.org/>

Case 22: Sustainable Food Places, United Kingdom

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Sustainable Food Places UK

One or two key features: brings together pioneering food partnerships across the UK that are driving innovation and best-practice in all aspects of healthy and sustainable food

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running since 2020 (5-year Sustainable Food Places programme)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Starting with a handful of places in 2010 with funding of the Esmée Fairbairn Foundation from 2013 – 2019 the organization grew up to 80 SFPs today and reaching out internationally to spread the concept

Which ambitions and objectives:

1. establish a cross-sector food partnership in the UK involving local authorities, public sector, business, academia, third sector
2. Develop shared vision, strategy and action plan to enhance the importance of healthy and sustainable food
3. Working together to spread the vision beyond UK

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Since 2010 helping Sustainable Food Places through knowledge sharing, strategizing, advise and support to enable local food partnerships to drive changes to local policy and practice, provide grants

What external input and output: Funding from the Esmée Fairbairn Foundation & National Lottery Community Fund, knowledge exchange with international networks (such as ICLEI, C40, MUFPF)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Local food supply chains	Policy makers, businesses, local civil society	Food partnerships on local levels	Support of local Food partnerships through: webinars, networking, toolkits etc.	Dependent on the activity and compliance of local food actors; cannot completely predict/influence actual outcomes	Network of sustainable food places has significantly grown in the last decade	Increased funding for their actions until 2026, generally since 2010

Main sources: <https://www.sustainablefoodplaces.org/>

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Workshops, toolkits, coaching, networking	Adopting to needs of local food systems and including insights into work; not inclusive towards international supply chains	Actor consists of various organisations and members who are made up of business, farmers, civil society	Yes, joint goal is to have a radical shift in our food and farming system towards agroecological production, sustainable diets and an end to food waste	Works together with international city networks, such as ICLEI, C40, Eurocities

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Their goal is to inspire and support local food initiatives to succeed in changing local Food Systems. Their approach doesn't involve a proposed strategy but invites initiatives to think about their local system and what could be done to address its unsustainability

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This varies with the local community they work with. Best-Practices from their work are: Aberdeen becoming a Sustainable Fish City, Micro grant to 27 small businesses and food initiatives to adapt to covid (Belfast), Vertical Farming within Old Mills (Bradford), Halal Lamb Farm-to-Fork Feasibility (identifying key elements of local lamb supply chain (Bradford) and many more, to find [here](#).

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Empowering and encouraging the actors that know their food system best: civil society, local business and farmers to address the topic that is most urgent in the local context. The Toolkit provides guides and workshops on mapping food systems or approaching policymakers, ways of communications and funding opportunities.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Social, economic and environmental sustainability go hand in hand. What indicators are weighted most is up to the specific local community.

Main sources: <https://www.sustainablefoodplaces.org/>

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Case 23: Biocode, Finland

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Biocode / Finland

One or two key features: The company provides tools for calculating CO²-emissions for food system actors

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

bio<code

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The company was founded by the Association of ProAgraria Centres' and Mtech Digital Solutions', who sought solutions to decarbonise food production.

Which ambitions and objectives: Decarbonising food production

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The company started as providing CO²-emission calculating services, and has evolved into other innovations within the field of sustainable food system

What external input and output: Input: information from the companies who buy the services, output: Carbon footprinting

An illustration
(Product, service,
organisation change,

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Carbon emissions	Farms	Information on carbon footprint of the product	Finding information on emissions of the raw materials	Information available limits the calculations	Information on the carbon footprint of a specific product	Not specified
	Food processing companies	CO ² footprint labels				
	Grocery stores					
	Information processing company					

Main sources: biocode.io

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Quantitative information on emissions	The actor is building new products and providing innovations as well as growing the customer base on the first product	Cooperation with customers, but also other SFS actors such as developer organisations and the founding NGO	Reduction of CO ² -emissions of the food products	Reduction of emissions

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Actively developing and offering new products supporting the sustainability activities of food system actors.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Calculation of carbon emissions of food products, though food system – from field to fork, including processing and retail

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Calculating the emissions and thereby providing the opportunity to efficiently reduce emissions and verify the process.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Carbon footprint

Influences SDGs 12 responsible consumption and production, 13 climate action, 17 partnership for the goals

Main sources: biocode.io

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Case 24: Regional Networks for Fair Consumption (REKO), Nordic countries

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country REKO, Regional Networks for Fair Consumption, 500 groups in FINLAND and the Nordic Countries

One or two key features: From Producer to Consumer, without middlemen. Informal network of producers and customers

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The farmers and consumers have created the practice together in order to shorten the food chain and support local food producers

Which ambitions and objectives: The objectives are to provide a distribution model offering customers an opportunity to order products directly from the producer, without the need for middlemen

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The groups are run by volunteers, and with a very low level of organisation or bureaucracy

What external input and output: The collection point is provided by a local supermarket, and the platform for the network by Meta / Facebook

An illustration
(Product, service,
organisation change, ...)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Distribution network: Each region has two FB-groups: One for producers (instructing, information-sharing), and one for public (for making orders).	Producers and consumers	Local food products	Distribution at a specifically agreed location directly from producer to consumer	Rules for the producers are provided in a regional producer Facebook group	Short food chains	Varies, distribution for example once every second week
				Pre-approved customers, rules in the FB-group	Fresh products	
					Low rate of production	

Main sources: aitojamakuja.fi/en/what-is-reko

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Informal organization level	Adapts according to customer needs	Informal network in Facebook	Local food	Some informal cooperation within the REKO network
Low level of bureaucracy	Short distribution chains	Two-way interaction between producers and consumers	Minimally processed, safe food	Actors in the networks are generally interested in fair and sustainable food system, and enhance the objectives through various other channels
Easy access for farmers			Fair and just trade for everyone	
Large variety of product groups represented				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Short production and distribution chains generate less emissions. Local food markets support the social sustainability within the community. Actors in the networks are generally interested in fair and sustainable food system, and enhance the objectives through various other channels.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Long production chains, use of non-fresh food products, non-just distribution system, long travel distances of food products.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Organizing an informal network of producers and customers, who can agree on the orders via Facebook group

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The number of local REKO distribution networks.

Influences SDGs 1 no poverty, 2 zero hunger, 3 good health and well-being, 5 gender equality, 8 decent work and economic growth, 10 reduced inequalities, 11 sustainable cities and communities, 12 responsible consumption and production, 17 partnerships for the goals.

Main sources: aitojamakuja.fi/en/what-is-reko

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP7

Case 25: Vegan Challenge, Finland

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Vegan challenge / Finland

One or two key features: Challenges the participant to try vegan diet for one month for the climate in a positive way

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: 10 years of cooperation with public figures and influencers as well as ordinary consumers / food citizens. Long history of supporting vegan diets

Which ambitions and objectives: 8 reasons for motivation
Aiming at making vegan diet easy and fun, and for various kinds of consumers

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: NGO Oikeutta eläimille (justice for animals) is the operating organisation of Vegan Challenge. Over time, the challenge has transformed into a challenge aimed at regular consumers, not only for animal rights activists

What external input and output: Input: Challenging people to try vegan diet for one month by providing various ways of support: mentors, social media groups, recipes...
output: More people on vegan or partly vegan diet.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Vegan diet	NGO actors	Vegan food	Buying	Vegan diet to be followed	Vegan or semi-vegan diets	One month
	Public figures	Community	Preparing	Various incentives for action		
	Food citizens	Recipes				
	Food producers					
	Grocery Stores					

Main sources: vegaanihaaste.fi

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FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Transforming activism into an easily accessible form	Adapting into including varying motivations to try vegan diets	High level of interaction between actors on social media and via newsletter	Support for vegan diet	Works together with various clusters: Common goal is to support vegan diet.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The motivation for sustainability actions for participants vary from : environment, climate, water, health, animal production, not missing out, delicacies, peer support.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Animal production (with its various unwished effects for climate).

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Supporting vegan diet in a positive manner by not making consumers feel guilty of their choices but by encouraging the small steps to change in various ways.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Annual number of participants to the challenge.

Influences SDGs 6 clean water and sanitation, 12 responsible consumption and production, 13 climate action, 14 life below water, 15 life on land, 17 partnership for the goals.

Main sources: vegaanihaaste.fi

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP 7

Case 26: Refugees in the food system of a medium-sized city, Poland

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Refugees in the food system of a medium-sized city/ POLAND

One or two key features: Answer to unexpected Crisis

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Milan Pact Awards 2022	
WROCLAW	
Country	Poland
Population	642,700
Title of policy or practice	Refugees in the food system of a medium-sized city
Subtitle (optional)	The power of social capital as a key factor of responding to a food security threat in the context of the influx of refugees from Ukraine
URL video	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/3/folders/12hP4y3Gpn-DoMowEZzdvwPpza9deYPP8

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The refugee crisis has not only accentuated the need to have a local food policy but has also made people aware of the importance of social capital in grassroots activities responding to the crisis.

Which ambitions and objectives:

The described practice contributed to the spontaneous creation of a specific and efficient network of connections, inter alia, in the scope of securing access to food for the refugees, which is of our interest here. It was possible thanks to strong social capital, supported and built for many years. In fact, the food system, in which we were not interested until the signing of the Milan Pact, has successfully passed the test of "being sufficient" for everyone.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation:

The situation we experienced has contributed to mapping this network, to identifying its strengths and weaknesses, which in the future will result in its efficient and effective extension to include other entities and areas

What external input and output The economic impact means more than €2,000,000 of unplanned expenditure in the city. The refugee crisis has not only accentuated the need to have a local food policy but has also made people aware of the importance of social capital in grassroots activities responding to the crisis.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food aids	Government and non gov organizations, donors, food banks, gastronomic schools	Food aids	Coordination action to support refugees from Ukraina	It is an answer developed to a crisis and in that sense allowed to overcome traditional boundaries limiting actors collaboration and bureaucratic boundaries	Thanks to this, it was possible to immediately launch three large food distribution points in the city, run by the city and non-governmental organizations. In three months, more than 1.3 million meals were served in these places only. In addition to employees, nearly 2 thousand volunteers were permanently involved. The food was purchased by the self-government, received from donors, food banks and was prepared by gastronomic schools belonging to the self-government (more than 80 thousand meals).	February March and April 2022

Main sources: <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/projects/refugees-in-the-food-system-of-a-medium-sized-city/>

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
flexibility	All the actors are adapting to the situation of crisis	All actors interacted between each others	Yes	Each cluster work with other outside network locally or internationally

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

According to the data of the Union of Polish Metropolises, more than 3 million refugees from Ukraine came to Poland, of which more than 187 thousand chose Wrocław (in this number, over 42 thousand are children). In April 2022 23% of the city residents are Ukrainians, with the majority still needing care and support

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

In connection with the described practice, we define the following challenges:

- Maintaining contact with persons/companies/networks of residents willing to act/local social innovators.
- Mapping the centers of the network of connections, created intentionally and automatically, with regard to the channels of food flow to, from and through the city as the origin of the food system diagnosis in the city

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

the stimulation of enormous social capital, which – properly targeted – allowed to control the situation without paralyzing the city, while ensuring food security and protecting the dignity and autonomy of the refugees

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The social impact is the coordination of grassroots food transfers with the contribution and measures of the city, which prevented the food exclusion of thousands of refugees, mainly women and children

Main sources: <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/projects/refugees-in-the-food-system-of-a-medium-sized-city/>

